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Evaluating Twelve Media Literacy and Digital Skills Interventions

Work Package 3 – Deliverable 3.1

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Executive summary

REMEDIIS employed **pre- and post-test designs** to assess 12 media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) interventions across six European countries (Belgium, Estonia, Finland, Poland, Spain and the UK). Pre-tests measured sociodemographic data, digital skills, media literacy and expected uses and outcomes. Post-tests, both immediate and delayed, assessed similar metrics to gauge changes resulting from the interventions. Many of the evaluations had a low number of participants, limiting the generalisability of the findings. Since every intervention and evaluation was unique and different evaluation measures had to be used, this report presents the findings separately for each intervention, with no intention of comparing them.¹

Key findings on intervention impacts

While this Executive summary does not include far-reaching conclusions based on comparisons between the interventions due to difficulties in comparability, a few cross-cutting conclusions about ML&DS interventions more generally can be drawn:

- Participants generally reported **modest perceived gains in digital knowledge and skills**, although consistent challenges in navigating online environments and recognising misinformation persisted.
- **Confidence generally increased**, even if literacy and skills did not (confidence is also likely to have collateral benefits in areas other than those that were the explicit aims of the intervention).
- **In-service teachers** showed an increase in information navigation, wellbeing, social and **financial activities** post-intervention.
- **Elderly individuals** demonstrated improved digital skills and knowledge post-intervention, especially in their ability to **navigate information** and **use digital tools**, although challenges in social media use and online information evaluation remained.
- Participants who **did not have the national language as a first language struggled to participate** in these interventions and acquire ML&DS, even though they were often clear on the benefits of being able to engage with ICTs. When **translations** were offered, participants showed to have higher skill levels than anticipated.

Key insights for intervention evaluation design

The evaluation raised many insights around the process of evaluation and obstacles encountered in evaluating interventions:

- Ongoing **theoretical development needs to be connected to practice** for it to be useful for improving the design of evaluations and our **understanding of the outcomes** of the intervention, especially when it comes to **factors beyond the intervention's content and format**.
- In evaluations involving socially disadvantaged groups, there were considerable **complications in applying quantitative methods** robustly; observations, interviews and

¹ Report D3.2 uses comparative data only to draw conclusions about generalisable trends in the data.

other **more personalised forms of evaluation and measurement** should be considered since they yielded important insights.

- ML&DS evaluations should be **designed in line with the diverse needs** of target groups – for example disadvantaged youths and the elderly will approach the interventions and benefit in different ways, and evaluations need to reflect this.
- Success of the evaluation relied heavily on **instructor engagement**, particularly in overcoming **language barriers** and **low literacy** levels among the participants.
- The project highlights the importance of **flexible, user-friendly evaluation toolkits** to support the effective development and implementation of scalable ML&DS programme evaluations.

Future directions for research in evaluating ML&DS interventions

- In future research, time needs to be scheduled to establish good **relationships with intermediaries** who work with vulnerable individuals.
- Trust relationships with intermediaries and beneficiaries are key to being able to conduct **further research with larger, controlled samples**, especially for vulnerable groups that continue to be underrepresented in research and groups less likely to participate in interventions.
- Larger samples and **pre- and post-measurement with greater time lags** and incorporation of serial interventions are needed to validate the initial findings from REMEDIS.
- Instruments need to be adapted to the **needs of both the intermediaries** implementing the intervention **and the beneficiaries** in mind, with clear explanations on what the **range of things** are that might be **considered in evaluation** and why.
- While they understood the reasons for including digital skills measures, and observed the impacts on these, stakeholders did not completely grasp the ways in which or why **outcomes of various kinds** might be **meaningfully evaluated**, and findings on impacts were more confused. Future research needs to improve and validate these measures and engagement with stakeholders around these.
- Developing robust **evaluation instruments** and methodologies are crucial for accurately measuring intervention impacts, with a focus on addressing the **limitations** posed by low **participant numbers**, short-term or **one-off interventions**, and ensuring comprehensive pre- and post-test scenarios with the **integration of evaluation into the design** of longer-term interventions from the start.
- **Short instruments** measuring the different aspects of ML&DS as well as the outcomes of these interventions in vulnerable populations need to be further developed.
- Considering the **low levels of traditional** and **digital literacy** of many of the participants, evaluation instruments need to be developed keeping this in mind, and made available in **different languages** and **formats**.
- There is a delicate and complicated **balancing act between brevity, understandability** and **comprehensiveness** in measuring impact, which necessitates **variations in measurements for different groups** and complicates the evaluation of the effectiveness of interventions.

1 Introduction

1.1 The REMEDIS project

The REMEDIS (REthinking MEdia literacy and DIgital Skills) project is funded by the European Union's CHANSE (Collaboration of Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe) programme. The consortium involves seven academic partners from six countries and 14 non-academic cooperation partners. REMEDIS seeks to develop evidence-based approaches to develop and evaluate initiatives that foster media literacy and digital skills (ML&DS) to understand the impacts of ML&DS interventions in different life domains regarding positive outcomes.

REMEDIS adopts an innovative research strategy that first aims to identify and quantify the most salient driving factors for ML&DS from a lifelong perspective, and to synthesise the existing evidence concerning the perceived effectiveness of current interventions fostering ML&DS. REMEDIS pays special attention to target groups, including disadvantaged youths (NEETs, or not in education, employment or training), the unemployed, refugees, people from lower socioeconomic status groups,, carers of vulnerable young people and (future) teachers.

The REMEDIS project has four research objectives:

1. To improve existing theoretical knowledge about the actual outcomes of the interventions.
2. To improve and enhance existing ML&DS intervention strategies based on existing and emerging evidence.
3. To adopt advanced methods and develop and validate instruments for evaluating intervention strategies.
4. To produce evidence-based policy recommendations and develop a user-friendly, customisable evaluation toolkit.

1.2 The report

This report advances the second and third objectives of REMEDIS: enhancing current ML&DS intervention strategies and developing instruments for evaluating these strategies. It outlines the methodological approach of REMEDIS, including the identification of effective strategies for evaluations, understanding end beneficiaries, and determining the circumstances under which these strategies yield positive outcomes, such as broader digital inclusion and wellbeing. It also presents descriptive findings for each intervention based on surveys using a basic core instrument developed for the project, questions developed in collaboration with the partners and qualitative observational work.

2 Methodology

One aim of REMEDIS is to identify effective strategies, understand for whom these strategies work, and determine under what circumstances they yield positive outcomes, such as fostering inclusion and wellbeing. This approach aims to produce scientifically sound estimates of the intervention programme’s effectiveness, with a special focus on the REMEDIS target groups constituting vulnerable populations. The findings will provide valuable input for Work Package 4 (WP4), contributing to the validation and enhancement of ML&DS intervention evaluation strategies.

This report describes the results of the 12 ML&DS interventions, with two interventions conducted for each REMEDIS partner country. The overall goals, target groups and activities of the intervention are briefly described, followed by the methodology used for the pre- and post-test phases, detailing the types of questions asked in both tests. The findings are then presented, covering the participants’ digital lived environment (including access), and their responses to questions about media and digital literacy (knowledge and skills). Additionally, the (perceived) impact of the intervention and the participants’ learning experience are discussed based on the results from the evaluation.

2.1 Characteristics of the interventions

Table 1. Interventions included in REMEDIS

Country	Intervention	Partner organisation(s)	Description of the intervention
Belgium	Veilig Online (VO - Safe Online)	Gezinsbond, Child Focus	Individual courses targeting parents in vulnerable groups (e.g., low SES, low literacy) on different topics relating to digital parenting, such as cyberbullying, social media, gaming and children’s online privacy
Belgium	Alle ouders digitaal vaardig (AODV – All parents digitally literate)	Gezinsbond	A series of three workshops designed to teach basic digital skills to parents who lag behind digitally
Estonia	Opiq webinar	Star Cloud LLC	An introductory 1.5–2-hour webinar for teachers who use Opiq, i.e., interactive eBooks, to increase their specific digital skills and their confidence in using eTools

Estonia	ÕPIRAAM course (Teaching and Learning Framework)	Education and Youth Board of Estonia (Harno)	Three 2.5-hour webinars, supported by homework and activities, allow teachers to learn about their pupils' personalised self-assessment methods. They help improve teachers' digital skills by guiding them in using digital platforms and tools
Finland	Mediataitojen tukena digitaalisessa arjessa (Strengthening multiliteracy)	The Finnish Society on Media Education (FSME)	Interventions were conducted for vocational school students during school days, focusing on digital multiliteracy as part of everyday life
Finland	Hyvinvointialueen digipalvelut tutuiksi ikääntyneille (Digital wellbeing services pilot course for older people)	University of the Third Age (U3A) in Jyväskylä (JYU), Centre of Excellence of Ageing and Care (CoE AgeCare) project	Pilot course (1 day, 5.5 hours) developed to support elderly people's digital service use and information security aspects at an everyday level
Poland	Jak skutecznie uczyć seniorów korzystania z nowych technologii (How to effectively teach seniors how to use new technologies) (TSOP)	Open UJ platform, KIRE (Krakowski Instytut Rozwoju Edukacji) (Krakow Institute for the Development of Education), National Federation of Associations of Universities of the Third Age in Poland, Media Education Centre at Polish Radio Kielce	The training programme is delivered in an online course format (supported by the Open UJ platform) covering nine thematic modules related to effective digital inclusion. The programme is aimed at carers, trainers and future gerontological staff , minimising digital exclusion among older people
Poland	Otwarty i kreatywny nauczyciel przyszłości (The open-minded	Polish Society for Educational Technology and Media (Polskie Towarzystwo Technologii i	A training programme (at least 5 meetings x 2 hours + individual work) to strengthen basic digital competencies and teachers' digital competence in the creation

and creative teacher of the future) (OTF) Mediów Edukacyjnych), IH Bielsko-Biała of open educational resources (video tutorials) for people in the formal and informal education system

Spain			This eight-week programme, comprising 35 hours for teachers and 14 hours for students, is designed to prevent violence against women in digital spaces and to promote gender cyber-coexistence. Targeting both teachers and secondary school students , it leverages service-, project- and problem-based learning approaches. These methods empower students by reinforcing critical thinking skills, empathy, emotion management and digital literacy
	Cibermanagers por la Igualdad (Cybermanagers for equality)	PantallasAmigas	
Spain			This educational project aims to enhance the critical evaluation skills of both secondary school teachers and students regarding the information they receive through social networks. The project focuses on improving their ability to recognise reliable sources and distinguish between rigorous and unreliable information
	Desfake	Verificat	
UK			One-to-one sessions to provide online support for people from low SES and jobseekers to develop digital skills and knowledge
	Digital Champions	Citizens Online (CO)	
UK			Three-week in-person digital skills course on how to use smartphones for everyday life, aimed at people on a low
	Digital literacy programme	CodeYourFuture (CYF)	

2.2 Methodology for evaluation

The evaluation process consisted of a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to gather information from different parties involved in the interventions, such as intervention end beneficiaries, volunteers and staff from partner organisations.

Based on the REMEDIS theory of change, the objective was to evaluate end beneficiaries' media literacy, digital skills and uses and outcomes of internet use before the intervention as well as the intervention's impact on these and how this was influenced by the characteristics of the intervention and the way the interventions were implemented. Additional details about the questionnaire development are presented in d'Haenens *et al.* (2024).

Design

A core part of REMEDIS was the development of a quantitative evaluation instrument that could be applied in various settings and with diverse groups of end beneficiaries to evaluate the intervention's impact on ML&DS, uses and outcomes of internet use. The evaluation instruments were adapted to the intervention's format and purpose. Therefore, while the project had designed a core questionnaire, the instruments applied did not contain the same questions across the interventions. For the base design, different instruments were developed for the pre- and post-tests.

Questionnaires and composite scales

This section describes the core design of the questionnaires, adaptations for each intervention are described in the sections that discuss the results per intervention.

The questionnaire was structured in the following way (see Appendix):

Part A enquired about the socio-demographics (age, gender, education level and occupation) and personal wellbeing of participants.

Part B consisted of two different indicators related to access. The first related to the average number of different devices each participant had access to, and the proportion of participants who only had access to a smartphone. For digital skills and knowledge, scores on each skill domain were calculated following the guidelines of the youth Digital Skills Indicator (yDSI) from the Youth Skills (ySKILLS) project (Helsper *et al.*, 2021):

- Technical and operational – the proportion of skills items at a high level.
- Information navigation and processing, communication and interaction, content creation and production – the proportion of skills at a high level and the number of correct answers to knowledge items in the corresponding domain.

For example, a person would receive a score of 100% on a scale when they responded 'Very true of me' (5) to all the skills items and got the answers correct for all knowledge items.

Averages are calculated based on the number of items responded to, which might be different from the total number of items. If a participant responded to only three out of five items, the proportion would be calculated based on the three items instead of the total five items related to, for example, communication and interaction skills.

The overall score measures digital skills across various dimensions, calculated by averaging proportions from different sections of the assessment. If digital skills questions (Part B) were not included in the post-test, the overall score was based on the percentage of participants who indicated in the post-test that they already knew how to undertake activities before the intervention

Part C measured uses of the internet in the pre- and post-tests as well as intentions for future use in the immediate post-test.

Part D measured outcomes in the pre- and post-tests. In the post-test uses and outcomes were combined.

Uses: This score reflects the proportion of participants who used the internet for different purposes (e.g., information, social activities, finance, education, work) independent of the outcome.

Future use: This score is based on how many participants indicated they might or definitely would use the internet for specific activities in the future.

Outcomes: The score is calculated based on the percentage of participants satisfied with the outcomes of their internet use (Part C) and the proportion who now expected themselves to achieve certain positive outcomes and avoid negative ones (Part D).

Finally, the scores for the overall uses and overall outcome dimensions were calculated by averaging the scores from each dimension.

Pre-test (see Figure 1)

Part A focused on gathering pre-intervention sociodemographic and wellbeing data, while Part B assessed digital skills, media literacy and digital knowledge. Part C of the pre-test evaluated uses and outcomes across various domains before or at the start of the intervention.

Figure 1. Pre-test: Interventions that applied different measures

Note: interventions in which aspect was measured indicated with the following numbers²:

- | | |
|---------------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. Belgium – Veilig Online (VO) | 6. Finland – FSME |
| 2. Belgium – AODV | 7. Poland – TSOP |
| 3. Estonia – Opiq | 8. Poland – OTF |
| 4. Estonia – ÕPIRAAM (Harno) | 9. Spain – Cibermanagers |
| 5. Finland – U3A | 10. Spain – Desfake |

² Interventions listed here as number 9, 10 and 11 did not use the core questionnaire in the pre-test. Interventions 9 and 10 only had a post-test, the evaluation for intervention 11 is still in progress.

Post-test (see Figure 2)

Two post-test options were available: an immediate test given at the end of the intervention session or a delayed test administered some time after the intervention. Both immediate and delayed post-tests could reuse questions from Parts A and B. The immediate post-test focused on future uses and outcomes (Part D), while the delayed post-test served as a follow-up conducted well after the intervention, reusing pre-test questions from Part C.³

Figure 2. Post-test: Interventions that applied different measures

Note: interventions in which aspect was measured indicated with the following numbers:

- | | |
|------------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. Belgium – VO | 6. Finland – FSME |
| 2. Belgium – AODV | 7. Poland – TSOP |
| 3. Estonia – Opiq | 8. Poland – OTF |
| 4. Estonia – ÖPIRAAM (Harno) | 9. Spain – Cibermanagers |
| 5. Finland – U3A | 10. Spain – Desfake |

³ See the separate sections for each intervention for information on which format was used for pre-, and post-tests

2.3 Conclusions around evaluation methodologies

One key issue was that it was often **hard to translate the theory of change** underpinning the project into practical evaluation measures that made sense to partner organisations, those implementing the evaluations and the participants in the interventions. This was partly due to a lack of time for establishing a good working relationship and co-development workshops with the partner organisations. This meant a **dropout of organisations** in Spain and a delay in the implementation of the evaluation of the projects.

Sufficient time was not always available **to establish relationships** of trust with the organisations and those delivering the interventions. For example, time pressures complicated the co-development process and buy-in for evaluation in Finland. This led to the use of instruments that were not the final ones original envisioned as REMEDIS partners, and **made results less comparable**.

Across all the interventions, the crucial role of **those delivering the intervention** to the success of intervention programmes was clear. For example, in Belgium, discussions with Gezinsbond and Child Focus highlighted that despite variations in experience and teaching styles, their ability to engage and interact with the participants was crucial, especially for those facing challenges such as language barriers or low literacy levels. The same was true in the UK where there were many individuals who did not have English as a first language. Deploying a co-instructor and/or someone who is fluent in the participant's language is essential in these cases. The piloting of a course in Finland also showed that the competence of the instructor alongside the role of the materials in the interventions (topic) were the main factors that promoted positive outcomes.

Besides the content and delivery of the intervention, issues related to the **availability and quality of physical or material resources** play a role in the intervention as well as the evaluation. Even when skills provision was the main aim of the intervention, access and quality infrastructure remained obstacles. For example, in the UK both Citizens Online and the Good Things Foundation⁴ found that providing (cheap) data access for mobile phones and devices such as smartphones or tablets could be key to people taking up the course, enabling them to reap the benefits of the intervention and complete the evaluation. Similarly, there were frequent disruptions in connectivity and functioning of devices, especially in more remote areas where interventions took place, which made completing the course, let alone the evaluation, very difficult.

Another issue for the evaluation of many of the interventions was **a small sample size**, either because the intervention had few participants or because there was low participation in the evaluation itself. In some countries, the evaluation and the questionnaires were not adjusted to the intervention or discussed sufficiently with those implementing or participating in the

⁴ The Good Things Foundation was also a REMEDIS partner in the UK. However, given that they do not carry out ML&DS interventions but support organisations running them, they were not included in this work package.

intervention. The participants queried the relevance of the questions asked and response rates were low. For example, this was the case for the pre-service teacher intervention Opiq in Estonia. In some instances, this had to do with the content of the course more than the evaluation. In Poland, while overall impressions of the course were positive, participants suggested adding new content, such as promoting professional profiles and expanding the edtech palette, something not explicitly considered in the evaluation that might have turned participants off from responding to the post-questionnaire.

For some interventions, there was **inequity in who participated**, which was reflected in the evaluation. In Belgium and the UK, addressing the gender imbalance in participation will be important for future evaluations, with three-quarters of the participants being women in Veilig Online, and all or almost all participants being women in Alle ouders digitaal vaardig (AODV) and Citizens Online interventions. These interventions in these particular locations need to explore alternative venues and times to attract more male participants, such as lunchtime workshops at workplaces or sports club canteens, for example.

Incentives should be provided where possible to both volunteers and those participating in the evaluation, especially when these are vulnerable groups experiencing complications in getting to and completing participation in the interventions in the first place.

The **duration of an intervention and associated fatigue** are key to evaluation as much as to how it might impact participation and dropout. For some groups, it is better to have shorter and more frequent interventions with short evaluations. For others, longer interventions work with a longer pre- and post-evaluation instrument. For example, elderly people in Finland showed that digital skills can be taught in an intensive one-day course.

However, **too much content** in the intervention and the measurement created fatigue, confusion and dropout in response. Innovative tools, like online chats, created frustration as people had to adjust to new and constantly changing technologies. In the UK, the Good Things Foundation found that they could not implement anything more than short text message-based questions because people often only logged in once to download material and had to answer a questionnaire, which reduced their willingness to take part in the actual intervention. Similarly, Citizens Online stressed that it should take no more than 15 minutes to complete the questionnaire to ensure a good turnout and so that data collection did not take a large proportion of time from the 1-hour sessions.

Exhaustion in the CodeYourFuture (CYF) evaluation might have been exacerbated due to the language barriers experienced by participants, who made great efforts to pay attention to a session in English and might have lost interest in collaborating. An important way to facilitate this is to integrate questionnaires with entry and exit questionnaires that participants have to complete as part of registration.

A mismatch between pre- and post-intervention measures caused issues in analysing change resulting from the intervention. In Belgium, Estonia and Finland, questions used in pre- and post- questionnaires were related to different dimensions, thus overall calculations represented different skills or uses. Consistency in measurement of the same dimensions pre-

and post-intervention would make comparisons for those dimensions more robust, even if not all domains are explored.

More definitive conclusions about the effect of the intervention along the lines of **RCT testing** would require an analysis of matched pairs between pre- and post-tests, control groups as well as larger samples with the application of the instrument in new and returning cohorts of participants. It seems very **unlikely that these ideal conditions will ever be present** in research with vulnerable populations, and alternative modes of collecting data such as through observation, collecting use data and qualitative interviews will be needed to support any quantitative evaluation. The U3A intervention in Finland concluded that an open space to express concerns and feelings towards digital technologies could be beneficial, since participants valued being heard outside of the formal evaluation process.

3 Findings from the evaluation studies

This section introduces each intervention separately in terms of its characteristics, the methodology for the evaluation used, findings related to the core areas of evaluation (participant access, skills, uses and outcomes of internet use pre- and post-intervention), as well as intervention-specific findings related to these aspects of digital inclusion. Since every intervention had a different delivery format, a different target group and different goals, not all aspects are equally represented in each intervention, which, even at this small scale, shows the richness and diversity of the landscape of ML&DS interventions in Europe.

Each section describes more detailed findings from the intervention (having given a description of the specifics of the intervention evaluation itself), followed by a description of overall insights from the core questions per domain (i.e., access, skills, uses and outcomes) where this was measured consistently, and in some cases we report on intervention-specific findings are reported around things that were particular to the intervention but not part of the core REMEDIS conceptual framework for evaluation.

3.1 Veilig Online (VO) – Belgium

Partner organisations

Child Focus and Gezinsbond enhance ML&DS for children and families in Belgium. Child Focus, dedicated to missing and exploited children, offers programmes to help young people navigate the digital world safely, focusing on online safety, privacy and responsible internet use. Gezinsbond, a family advocacy group, promotes media literacy through workshops, campaigns and resources, equipping families to critically evaluate digital content and maintain a healthy media relationship. Together, they contribute to creating positive and safer digital experiences for children and their families.

Intervention goals

Through a combination of informative content, real-life examples, video testimonials and practical tips, Veilig Online (Safe Online) aims at helping parents manage their children’s use of digital media.

Target group/vulnerability

Although Veilig Online initially aimed to engage all parents, there has been a concerted effort to reach those from disadvantaged backgrounds by partnering with grassroots organisations dedicated to combating poverty and exclusion. To ensure the programme is accessible to socially disadvantaged parents, the content and delivery methods – such as interactive website modules – have been rigorously tested with this demographic.

Furthermore, socially vulnerable parents are incentivised to participate through a favourable financial arrangement, as the programme is offered free of charge to these groups. The

updated programme is also actively promoted among organisations that work with these communities. Many participants face challenges such as having a migration backgrounds, language barriers, low literacy, limited education or unemployment.

Intervention format/activities

Veilig Online offers a comprehensive series of interactive training courses designed for parents navigating the complexities of digital and media influences on their children. Led by experienced trainers, each 2-hour session provides a supportive environment for parents to engage in meaningful discussions, share experiences and gain valuable insights. Sessions are conveniently held in the evenings at various community locations across Belgium, including schools, libraries and Houses of the Child, which comprise several organisations supporting parents with childcare and upbringing⁵. The programme covers a wide range of topics, including digital toddlers and preschoolers, social media, internet and privacy, gaming, cyberbullying, and online relationships and sexuality.

3.1.1 Methodology

The Veilig Online training sessions were conducted between November 2023 and March 2024. Before the start of the first session, the REMEDIS team carried out a brief evaluation. Following the session, an online post-assessment was administered to gauge the perceived impact of the intervention. The pre-test assessments used questions from Parts A, B and C of the REMEDIS questionnaire, while the post-assessments employed Parts B and D (see Figure 3), which were linked to the previous responses using unique ID codes generated by the participants.

Figure 3. Questionnaire application overview – Veilig Online

⁵ “Houses of the Child” is an umbrella organisation of initiatives supporting families in child upbringing, in areas such as day care, health care, and leisure. (Expecting) parents can contact the House of the Child with questions relating to pregnancy, childbirth, caring for babies, toddlers, and children. Additionally, Houses of the Child serve as community meeting spaces for parents and their children, where events and workshop on the themes outlined above are also regularly organised.

Sample size, age and gender: 185 participants (75% women) with an average age of 41 (ranging from 24 to 71) in the Veilig Online sessions completed the pre-assessment, of which 35 participants also completed the post-assessment.

Educational background and family composition: Only 4% of participants are in part-time or full-time education, while 96% work part-time or full-time. Among the participants, 90% are married or cohabiting and 8% are divorced or single. On average, they have two children aged 9–10.

3.1.2 Findings

Access

Almost all the 185 pre-assessment participants reported having either two (n = 66; 36%) or three (n = 110; 60%) devices at home to access the internet. The most commonly used devices were smartphones (n = 183; 99%), followed by computers (n = 176; 95%), while tablets (n = 115; 62%) were used less frequently. Notably, smartphones were the only device for internet access for nearly 3% of the 185 participants.

Digital Literacy

Most participants indicated that they knew how to secure their smartphones, computers or tablets (n=166; 90%), and they also knew how to store photos or documents on iCloud or Google Drive (n = 158; 85%). However, they were less familiar with browsing in incognito mode (n = 106; 57%).

Uses post-test

The intervention has contributed to the participants' different uses of ICTs. The highest percentage increase was for finding information online to answer specific questions (69%), followed by searching for quality information on topics of interest (60%).

More than half the participants said they had become better at online activities relating to information navigation, such as searching for information to help in the process of recognising misleading information (62%), using the internet or apps to get health advice (57%), and avoiding apps or websites containing harmful information (54%).

The training did not focus on the information navigation related to health and government services, and for most there was no increase in use in this area, such as recognising false health information (54% did not find they would be better at doing this after the intervention than before) or finding online government information (44%). Increases in general information literacy and information search outcomes did not seem to have positive spillover effects to other areas.

Intervention-specific findings: parental mediation skills and outcomes of internet use

Post-intervention results showed that parents participating felt more knowledgeable and confident in supporting their children's internet use and dealing with negative online experiences. They reported improved abilities to talk about safe internet practices, although

many still struggled with more specific tasks such as avoiding harmful websites and recognising false information.

Interestingly, those already experienced in discussing internet use with their children reported fewer positive outcomes, except in contexts related to online purchases. These parents likely started with higher baseline scores. This means they had less room for improvement, which could explain why the perceived learning gains were modest. Their smaller gains might not reflect the ineffectiveness of the intervention, but rather that they were already well-informed or skilled in the relevant areas.

3.1.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital skills

Overall, the proportion of technical and operational skills at a high level was 54%. Questions related to information, communication and content creation skills were asked in the post-test. Proportions of skills at a high level were 2% and 6% for information and communication skills, respectively, and nobody reported skills at a high level for content creation skills.

Digital Literacy

Participants reported having used the internet in higher proportions for activities related to informal learning (62%), followed by social (30%) and wellbeing (26%) activities. Overall, participants undertook around 39% of activities across the three domains.

The overall score for the post-test showed an important increase to 61%. Even when increases were found in all three domains, it was particularly noticeable in wellbeing (57%) and social activities (56%), thus informal learning reported a slight improvement (69%).

3.1.4 Key insights

Parents participating in the evaluation generally had good access to digital devices, with smartphones being the most common device. A notable difference was observed in the pre-test regarding the various domains of use, with a preference for informal learning compared to the lower levels of social uses and uses relating to wellbeing. For several use domains, post-intervention increases in participants' perceived abilities to engage in these uses were observed, most notably for uses relating to finding and evaluating quality information and avoiding potentially misleading or harmful information. Overall, the intervention appears to have had a moderate impact on participating parents' confidence and communication skills regarding their children's digital activities, although specific areas of digital literacy remain challenging.

3.2 Alle ouders digitaal vaardig (AODV) – Belgium

Partner organisation

Gezinsbond is a family advocacy group that promotes media literacy through workshops, campaigns and resources, helping families critically evaluate digital content and maintain a healthy media relationship. Together, Gezinsbond and families, create a safer, more informed digital environment.

Intervention goals

Central to the programme is the use of parents’ own smartphones, enabling hands-on learning experiences. The primary goal is to cultivate an atmosphere of connection, trust and openness, encouraging participants to voice their digital queries and concerns freely. By fostering dialogue and equipping parents with tools to recognise and respond to potential online risks, the programme promotes greater awareness and communication within families, ultimately enhancing digital literacy and fostering safer online environments for all.

Target group/vulnerability

The Alle ouders digitaal vaardig - AODV (All parents digitally literate) initiative, spearheaded by Gezinsbond and backed by the Flemish Government, offers a series of three tailored interactive workshops to support parents with limited digital proficiency.

Intervention format/activities

Designed to foster a safe and inclusive learning environment, each workshop series comprises three engaging sessions, typically conducted weekly, in intimate groups of five to eight participants. Using informal educational methods and peer-to-peer interaction, a knowledgeable trainer facilitates and tailors each session to the group’s needs and inquiries. Workshop activities include dynamic elements such as debates, quizzes, hypothetical scenarios and practical exercises, all tailored to address real-life online situations and challenges.

3.2.1 Methodology

AODV ran from October to December 2023. Immediately at the end of each of the three sessions, a short post-assessment was carried out. After the first and second session, questions from parts A, B and C of the REMEDIS questionnaire were used to capture a baseline of participants’ internet access, skills, uses and outcomes. After the third session, questions from Part D assessed the perceived impact of the sessions on participants’ internet use. All seven participants completed the first and second questionnaire, while the third questionnaire was only completed by four out of these seven participants.

Figure 4. Questionnaire application overview – Alle Ouders Veilig Online- Belgium

Sample

Gender and education: All participants were women, with an average age of 41 (ranging from 35 to 52).

Occupation: Four participants reported being unemployed, two were working part-time and one looking after the home and the children.

Family composition: Four were married or cohabiting, two were divorced and one was single. All the women were mothers: four had two children each, while the remaining three had between six and nine children.

3.2.2 Findings

Post-test 1, Access

Five mothers reported having one media device at home (a smartphone) that they used to access the internet, while the remaining two indicated they had two such devices. Among these, the smartphone was the most used, followed by the computer and tablet, which were significantly less preferred.

Post-assessment 2, Uses

As a result of the intervention, three out of four participants felt that they had become more knowledgeable in searching for online information to address specific questions they had. All four participants agreed that they had slightly improved in finding information online about topics that interested them due to the intervention. Half the participants reported increased confidence in using technology, such as the internet and smartphone, after the intervention. However, the other half felt less confident in this area following the workshop.

Regarding acquiring knowledge online to answer specific questions, three mothers felt they had improved after the intervention, while one indicated she still did not know how to do this. All four participants agreed that they had gained more knowledge from the training when it came to finding information about topics that interested them. Interestingly, all four also reported that they had improved in finding high-quality information online after the training.

This contrasted somewhat with their responses to whether they felt better at recognising false or misleading information, with half indicating they felt capable of doing so after the training.

When we asked participants to assess their handling of concrete health information, particularly the use of apps for sports and fitness advice, two indicated that they still would not do this because they did not know how to, while the other two reported that they had improved in this area after the training.

Intervention-specific findings: parental mediation and outcomes

This intervention also asked about knowledge and mediation of their children’s internet and social media use. Since the total number of participants in the sample was small, conclusions about the contribution of the intervention are limited. Results did not show any meaningful improvements across dimensions such as whether they felt more confident in supporting their children, discussing safe internet practices and encouraging them to explore and learn from the internet. Furthermore, questions related to future use and expected outcomes in informal learning, wellbeing and social activities were raised.

3.2.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital Literacy

Using participants’ responses in Part D (uses and outcomes) it was calculated that they knew how to carry out the activities enquired about in 63% of the cases after the intervention, although 56% reported that they already knew how to do so before the intervention. In other words, there was an increase of 7% in the activities they knew how to do due to the intervention.

Uses

In the pre-test, activities related to informal learning were the most frequently engaged in by participants (86% of activities), followed by social (71%) and wellbeing (57%) activities. Overall, participants reported using the internet for 71% of the activities surveyed.

In the post-test, participants planned to undertake about 75% of all activities in each domain in the future, with a spread across different types of activities. Therefore, a decrease in future use of the internet for informal learning activities was reported, while uses in wellbeing and social activities had an increase of 18% and 4%, respectively.

Outcomes

The results of the first post-test show a high level of optimism, with all participants satisfied with the outcomes in the social dimension, 86% satisfied with the outcomes in the wellbeing dimension and 83% in the informal learning dimension. On average, participants were satisfied with the outcomes of 90% of the activities enquired about.

3.2.4 Key insights

Participants in AODV had to rely mainly on smartphones to access the internet given that it was the only device for the majority of them. They engaged in various activities related to informal learning (86%), wellbeing (57%), or social interactions (71%), and were generally satisfied with the outcomes of these activities. The intervention contributed to the participants' skills and uses/outcomes, with participants generally happy with outcomes obtained, and feeling that they had improved in the surveyed skill dimensions.

3.3 Opiq webinar – Estonia

Partner organisation

Star Cloud LLC developed Opiq, a cloud-based learning platform featuring digital textbooks, interactive assignments and assessments from top Estonian publishers. Aligned with the Estonian curriculum, Opiq supports innovative, interactive education, and was used extensively during the Covid-19 pandemic. Compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Opiq offers up-to-date materials and teacher training. Operating in six countries since 2014, Star Cloud LLC partners with content providers, schools and the public sector.

Intervention goals

The intervention empowers in-service teachers to effectively use digital instructional and assessment resources. Through interactive webinars, teachers learn to integrate Opiq's digital materials, textbooks and self-assessment tests into their teaching. Opiq offers secure, high-quality resources, enhancing instructional quality and streamlining lesson preparation. The platform supports formative assessments, data-driven decisions and digital tracking, allowing teachers to monitor student progress, provide timely feedback and personalise learning.

Target group

The Opiq webinars target in-service teachers new to or interested in the platform. Although not a vulnerable group, teachers significantly impact students' wellbeing and learning outcomes, and these students come from a wide variety of backgrounds. For students, using digital resources reduces the need for heavy textbooks, promoting physical comfort and enhancing engagement through advanced, pedagogically enriched education. This helps make quality education accessible to all young people.

Intervention format/activities

Opiq webinars are held regularly to introduce new features and improve teachers' instructional techniques. Before the autumn session, Star Cloud LLC surveys teachers to understand their current usage and desired skills, shaping the webinar content. The 1.5–2-hour interactive webinars are offered on three dates, showcasing the Opiq teacher interface. Tailored to participant feedback, the webinars encourage pre-submitted questions to address specific needs and ensure focused discussions.

3.3.1 Methodology

The three Opiq webinars took place between 6 and 26 October 2023. Pre-test data was collected during this period, and post-test data between 11 and 12 December. Despite reminder emails, response rates remained low and unchanged. In order to boost responses, a raffle for bookstore gift cards was held for those completing both surveys.

Parts A, B and C of the REMEDIS questionnaire were used for the pre-test, while Part D was used for the post-test. Minor modifications included adding questions about access to Opiq (user licence) and prior use. Irrelevant items, such as job-seeking opportunities in Part C's work module, were excluded as all participants were employed in-service teachers. Part D's education module, originally for students, was adapted in the post-test to highlight potential benefits for teachers (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Questionnaire application overview – Opiq

Sample: Out of 132 webinar participants, 15 completed the pre-test and 7 completed the post-test. The post-test was only sent to those who completed the pre-test. Due to technical issues, only six participants' data could be matched. The response rate was 11% for the pre-test, 5% for the post-test and nearly 5% for completing both. In the following findings, we analyse the answers from the latter subset of six individuals who completed both pre- and post-intervention surveys. Participants in this study exhibited a profile characterised by predominantly higher levels of education and professional activity. This suggests that many participants likely have substantial exposure to and familiarity with technology in their daily lives.

Age and gender: The surveyed teachers' ages ranged from 44 to 58 (mean = 54). Gender distribution showed that one participant was male while five participants were female.

Educational and professional background: All six participants who completed both assessments had attained at least a Master's degree. Four were employed full-time, working at least 30 hours per week, while two worked part-time, ranging from 8 to 29 hours per week.

None reported being unemployed, retired or permanently disabled. Four had participated in paid, unpaid or volunteer work within the last month.

3.3.2 Findings

Access

All six participants reported using a computer, whether desktop or laptop, and an equal number reported using a smartphone that provided internet access or allowed app downloads. Three of the participants reported using a tablet or eReader, such as an iPad or Kindle, while none reported using a game console.

Uses and outcomes: Informal learning

Pre-intervention

In the past month, participants engaged in informal learning activities related to information navigation. Four participants reported successfully finding information online to answer their questions and were satisfied with the results, while two were not satisfied. Similarly, when encountering differing opinions on platforms, such as newspapers and discussion boards, four were happy with the outcome and two were not.

Post-intervention

In the post-test, all six participants indicated they would seek information online. Five felt competent in finding quality information, with one gaining confidence post-intervention. However, only three felt confident in discerning suspicious sites, while the other three remained unsure.

Findings concerning informal learning showed a positive tendency of the intervention to increase participants' information navigation, including confidence in their ability to find useful and high-quality information.

Uses and outcomes: Wellbeing

Pre-intervention

Teacher participants were asked about encountering offensive content and information leading to poor health decisions online. Five participants reported encountering offensive content in the past month, but none found information that negatively impacted their health decisions.

Post-intervention

All teachers surveyed intended to use the internet and apps for health advice in the coming months: four were definite and two were considering it. For exercise and nutrition, five might use them, while one definitely would. Two were unsure how to avoid harmful apps or websites, another two knew how to avoid them, and the remaining two learned this skill during the intervention. Additionally, five already knew how to find information to understand problems or issues of interest, while one person acquired this skill during the intervention.

Regarding wellbeing, the findings indicated enhanced intent and confidence among participants in using online resources for health-related purposes. This suggests a positive influence of the intervention on participants' attitudes towards digital wellbeing resources, potentially leading to improved health-seeking behaviours.

Uses and outcomes: Social activities

Pre-intervention

Five participants successfully searched for information on government or public services, while one had not attempted this in the past month. Regarding negative experiences, two received annoying or embarrassing messages, but none reported that the internet and mobile phones made interacting with others more difficult.

Post-intervention

Post-intervention, three participants now knew how to handle online bullying or harassment compared to two who already knew and one who still did not know. Additionally, five were confident in contacting friends and family, with one learning this during the study. Five already knew how to handle annoying or embarrassing messages, while one learned this during the intervention. Three knew how to avoid frustration in online communication beforehand, and the other three learned during the intervention.

In terms of **social activities**, there was an increase in participants' intent and confidence in being able to achieve positive outcomes of internet use for social purposes post-intervention, especially in handling online bullying and harassment. This suggests that the intervention may have reinforced participants' social support networks and reduced negative online experiences, thereby enhancing their overall digital socialisation.

Uses and outcomes: Work and education (occupation)

Pre-intervention

All participants had used the internet or mobile phone for work in the last month and were happy with the results. Additionally, five were satisfied with online information search results, while one had not tried searching online in the past month. Five had searched for work-related information online in the last month. No participants reported trouble accessing work materials online or being forced to work in a certain way due to the internet or mobile phone.

Post-intervention

When asked about time-saving abilities using the internet, five participants reported they already knew how to save time in their jobs, and one learned this during the intervention. For online networking (e.g., LinkedIn), two felt confident prior to the intervention, one learned during the intervention, one did not know how, one was not interested, and another one did not wish to answer. Five participants reported they already knew how to access work materials online or via email, while one participant learned this skill during the intervention. Four

participants were already knowledgeable about choosing the right technology for homework or assignments, and two acquired this knowledge during the intervention.

In terms of occupation (work and education), participants expressed high confidence in using digital tools for work-related activities both pre- and post-intervention. The intervention improved some participants' time-saving and networking abilities. In particular, during the Opiq webinars, participants learned how to use technology for homework assignments. This underscores the importance of ongoing digital skills training and support to facilitate professional advancement and productivity among in-service teachers and increased future use and positive outcomes in this area.

Uses and outcomes: Financial activities and literacy

Pre-intervention

Regarding buying products or services online, one participant was dissatisfied, while five were satisfied with the service or product. All six participants had successfully used online financial services, such as banking and finding insurance, in the past month. Only one had bought poor-quality products online in the past month, and none had lost money due to fraud or scams.

Post-intervention

In terms of financial literacy, one participant was unsure about saving money by finding better prices, while five knew they could. Three already knew how to identify fake ads, and the other three learned during the study. Three already knew how to avoid scams or fraud, one learned during the study and two still did not know how. Regarding unnecessary purchases, five already knew how to avoid them, and one learned during the study.

Participants exhibited a shift in ability to achieve positive financial outcomes, with increased recognition of scams, fraud, fake ads and poor-quality products. Although all participants were already successfully using online financial services before the intervention, enhanced financial literacy and decision-making skills are vital for online safety. These results are somewhat surprising given that the intervention did not cover media or financial literacy, but could be considered as secondary outcomes of participants' increased confidence and digital skills practice.

3.3.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital Literacy

Based on the questions related to digital skills, participants had 45% of skills at a high level. Information navigation and evaluation skills presented the best results, with 63% at a high level, followed by technical and operational and communication and interaction skills – both at 50% – and with a considerable distance, content creation and production skills, at 17%.

Uses

In the pre-test, participants' scores were notably high across all dimensions, having an overall proportion of 94%. The best cases were for informal learning and finance activities, both at 100%, followed by work (92%) and wellbeing and social activities, both with 89% of activities reported.

For the post-test, the overall score was virtually the same (95%), having wellbeing, social, finance and education activities at 100% for future use, and a slight decrease in work activities to 75%.

Outcomes

Participants had a good overall perception of their outcomes in the pre-test. Their satisfaction with outcomes at work was 100%, followed by social (94%) and finance (92%) dimensions. Last, wellbeing and informal learning had a proportion of satisfaction with the perceived outcomes of 78% and 67%, respectively.

Nevertheless, the participants were less optimistic at the post-test regarding the expected outcomes after the intervention. Expected outcomes in work and social domains were 83% in both cases, followed by wellbeing and finance (67% each), and last, informal learning, with 50%. Overall, participants expected to achieve 58% of the outcomes enquired about across all dimensions.

3.3.4 Key insights

The most surprising aspect of the Opiq intervention was the improvement in participants' financial media literacy in consumer awareness areas, despite the intervention not specifically covering media or financial literacy. This suggests that the increased confidence and digital skills practice gained from the intervention had secondary benefits, potentially enhancing participants' ability to recognise scams, fraud, fake ads and poor-quality products.

3.4 ÕPIRAAM course – Estonia

Partner organisation

The Education and Youth Board of Estonia (Harno) is a division of Estonia's Ministry of Education and Research. Harno is crucial in implementing Estonian education and youth policy, from primary to higher education. It promotes high-quality, modern and accessible education in Estonia, helping individuals to craft personalised professional development paths.

Intervention goals

ÕPIRAAM, the Teaching and Learning Framework, enhances educational effectiveness by guiding teachers in creating secure, efficient and innovative learning experiences across five areas: effective learning and motivation, mental health, physical health, digital competencies, and relevant instructional resources. It addresses contemporary educational challenges, balancing student wellbeing with academic progress. The framework integrates online testing to improve digital learning through well-designed assessments, equipping educators with the skills to maximise the benefits of digital self-assessment. Teachers are trained to use digital

tools for student self-assessments, aligning these with educational objectives to foster personalised, informed learning experiences and improve learning outcomes.

Target group/vulnerability

The ÖPIRAAM course targets in-service teachers, requiring active classroom engagement for practical assignments. Unlike most REMEDIS target groups, teachers are not considered vulnerable. However, their work significantly impacts all students’ learning, development and wellbeing outcomes, including those who suffer hardship and exclusion.

Intervention format/activities

The ÖPIRAAM course includes six structured components in a webinar format: (1) contact seminar; (2) independent work 1 (exploring the ÖPIRAAM learning framework); (3) independent work 2 (self-monitoring tests with student); (4) intermediate seminar (reflecting on progress and discussing challenges); (5) independent work 3 (analysing test results for data-driven decision-making); and (6) contact seminar (feedback).

3.4.1 Methodology

The ÖPIRAAM course ran from 24 October to 21 November 2023, with data collection starting at the first seminar and ending in December. Pre- and post-questionnaire data were collected, with reminders sent twice to participants. A raffle for bookstore gift cards incentivised participation; anonymity of the participants was ensured by deleting all contact information after the raffle.

Out of 60 participants, 14 completed the pre-test (23% response rate for pre-test) and 11 also completed the post-test (18% response rate for completing both). In the following findings we analyse the answers from the latter subset of 11 individuals who completed both pre- and post-intervention surveys. This ensures a repeated measures approach where the respondents’ pre- and post-test data were linked, reducing between-subject variability when assessing any change in outcomes for this limited sample size.

The pre-test used Parts A, B and C of the REMEDIS questionnaire, with minor adjustments such as adding questions on motivation and obstacles for participation. Irrelevant items, such as job-seeking opportunities in Part C’s work module, were excluded as all participants were employed as in-service teachers. Part D’s education module, originally for students, was adapted for the post-test to highlight potential benefits for teachers (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Questionnaire application overview – ÕPIRAAM

Sample

In analysing the demographics of the 60 Estonian in-service teachers who took part in the Harno-delivered intervention, we focused on the subset of 11 individuals (18%) who completed both the pre- and post-intervention surveys in a repeated measures approach. When referring to participants in the following sections, the 11 individuals who participated in both the pre- and post-test are considered.

Educational background and family composition. Participants consisted of a group predominantly composed of well-educated and professionally active individuals, with a strong integration of technology into their daily lives. The majority held a Master's degree and were employed full-time, highlighting the relevance of considering their digital literacy and preferences when designing interventions.

Age and gender: The surveyed teachers had a mean age of 54 (range = 40–57). All participants in this subset identified as female.

Educational and professional background: Among the participants, one (9%) had completed secondary school, two (18%) held a Bachelor's degree, and the majority, eight (73%), had a Master's degree. Professionally, seven (64%) were working full-time and three (27%) were working part-time. None were unemployed, retired, permanently sick or disabled, in community or military service, taking care of the household, or looking after children or other people. One participant (9%) listed their professional situation as 'Other' as she was studying and working at the same time. Out of the eleven participants, nine (82%) had engaged in paid, unpaid or volunteer work in the last month while two (18%) had not.

3.4.2 Findings

The findings provide several insights across various domains, indicating potential changes in the behaviours and attitudes of in-service teachers in Estonia due to digital interventions. However, it is important to note the study's small sample size of 11 participants and the mismatch between some pre- and post-intervention measures, which calls for careful interpretation of these results.

Access

All participants reported using a computer, whether desktop or laptop, and ten reported using a smartphone that provided internet access or allowed app downloads. Five reported using a tablet or eReader such as an iPad or Kindle, while none reported using a game console. All participants reported having at least two devices to access the internet.

Uses and outcomes: Informal learning

Pre-intervention

Three participants had searched for answers online in the past month but were not satisfied with the results, while eight were satisfied.

Post-intervention

Nine participants definitely planned to seek information online in the next month, while two were considering it. Eight participants felt competent in finding quality information, and two gained confidence post-intervention, while one remained unsure. However, results were less encouraging for identifying suspicious sites, with only three confident in their ability and eight remaining unsure.

In terms of information navigation, there is a suggestion of a possible shift towards increased recognition and use of online resources. Before the intervention, participants generally reported satisfaction with their online information searches. Afterwards, a significant majority expressed their intention to engage more in information navigation activities, hinting at growing awareness of digital learning platforms' value and accessibility.

Uses and outcomes: Wellbeing

Pre-intervention

All 11 participants had looked up information online in the past month about issues that interested them. Among them, eight were satisfied with the results while three were not. Regarding the use of sports, exercise and dietary advice or programs/apps, five had not used them while six had and were satisfied.

Post-intervention

Participants expressed varying intentions regarding health-related internet and app usage in the coming months. Two were not interested, four might use them and five would definitely use them. Similarly, for exercise and nutrition, two participants were not interested, three might use them and six would definitely use them.

Regarding wellbeing, there seems to be an enhancement in participants' intent and confidence in using online resources for health-related purposes. After the intervention, participants showed an increase in their interest in using health-related internet resources, indicating a positive trend towards embracing digital tools for wellbeing.

Uses and outcomes: Social activities

Pre-intervention

Nine participants had sought information on government or public services through digital means in the past month and were satisfied with the results, whereas one was unhappy with the results, and one had not attempted this. Regarding encounters with online behaviour, five participants reported receiving annoying or embarrassing messages in the past month, highlighting a prevalent issue. Additionally, two stated that online interaction had made interacting with others more difficult for them in the past month, suggesting potential barriers to digital communication.

Post-intervention

Nine participants intended to use the internet for problem-solving purposes in the coming months, while the remaining two might do so. Regarding handling annoying or embarrassing messages, six participants already knew how, one learned this during the intervention, two still did not know how and two did not want to answer.

In the domain of social activities, the study indicates a potential increase in participants' intent and confidence in using the internet for social purposes. Before the intervention, all participants used digital media for communication with family and friends. Post-intervention, all participants expressed an ongoing intent to continue this practice, coupled with increased confidence in using the internet for problem-solving.

Uses and outcomes: Work and education (occupation)

Pre-intervention

One participant had not tried using the internet or mobile for work in the past month, whereas ten had done so and were also satisfied. Two had not tried searching work-related information online in the past month, one had but was unhappy with the results, and eight were satisfied. Two participants had had trouble accessing online work materials in the past month while nine had not.

Post-intervention

One participant was not confident in saving time using the internet for work, four were unsure, five already knew how to save time and one learned how. Regarding working longer due to the internet, one participant already knew how to avoid this, three now knew, two still do not know, two did not want to answer and three did not understand the question. Nine expressed an intention to use the internet in the coming months to find study materials not available at school or the library, one said they might do so, and finally, one did not wish to answer. For signing up for online courses in the coming months, one was not interested, two might do this and seven would definitely do this.

In terms of occupation (work and education), the findings suggest the significance of digital skills in professional settings. Before the intervention, most participants were actively engaged in work activities using the internet or a mobile device. After the intervention, every participant

showed a clear interest in using these tools for work-related tasks, demonstrating heightened confidence in efficiently saving time and networking digitally. This underscores the potential need for ongoing digital skills training to facilitate professional growth and productivity for in-service teachers.

Uses and outcomes: Financial activities and literacy

Pre-intervention

Among the 11 participants, one had not tried buying products or services online in the past month, one had tried but was unhappy with the result and nine were happy with their experience. Regarding using financial services online, one was unhappy with the result and ten were happy with their experiences in the past month.

Post-intervention

One participant did not believe they could save money by finding better prices online, three were unsure and seven knew how to do this. Regarding identifying fake ads or poor-quality products, one did not think they could, six were unsure and four knew how. Four participants already knew how to avoid scams or fraud, three now knew, three still do not know and one did not want to answer. Seven participants already knew how to avoid wasting money on unnecessary purchases, one now knew, two still do not know and one did not want to answer.

Financial activities and literacy also indicated slight changes. Before the intervention, participants generally reported satisfaction with their online purchasing and financial service experiences. After the intervention, there was some increase in recognising scams and avoiding wasting money. These changes imply potential improvements in financial literacy and decision-making among participants.

3.4.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital Literacy

The four digital skills dimensions were measured, with an overall score of 29%. The highest score observed was for communication skills (42%), followed by technical and information skills (36% and 25%, respectively). Last, content creation skills had a substantially lower score of 11%.

Uses

Participants reported relatively high levels of use across all dimensions. Informal learning activities presented the lowest proportion of activities at 77%, and wellbeing presented a similar proportion at 79%. Work and social activities had similar proportions (86% and 88%, respectively), while finance-related activities reported the highest score at 95%. Overall, participants carried out 85% of the activities enquired.

When it comes to future use, participants reported in the post-test a similar overall proportion (89%). Despite some variations, all domains presented high proportions, with wellbeing and work the lowest, at 82% each, followed by finance (86%), education (95%) and social (100%) activities.

Outcomes

In the pre-test, participants reported experiencing positive outcomes across all dimensions, with an overall proportion of 86%. Outcomes related to work (100%), social (94%) and finance (92%) scored notably high scores, whereas outcomes in wellbeing and informal learning were relatively lower, at 78% and 67%, respectively.

The post-test consistently presented lower scores in all dimensions. The expected outcomes were particularly lower in informal learning (50%), while wellbeing and finance had the same results (67% in both cases), as well as social and work-related outcomes (83%). Overall, the proportion of perceived outcomes was 58%, clearly lower than the overall in the pre-test (86%).

3.4.4 Key insights

While the study's findings suggest potential changes in participant behaviours and attitudes across various domains due to the intervention, further research with larger samples and more directly comparable measures is needed to confirm these preliminary observations and to fully understand the effects of digital interventions on in-service teachers in Estonia.

Participants of the ÖPIRAAM intervention had extensive ICT access, with all using computers and most using smartphones. Their internet and mobile phone use for work was also high, with most having used these tools and being satisfied with them. However, their digital skills were relatively low, with an overall score of only 29% of skills at a high level, indicating a need for digital skills interventions even in this group of professionals working with ICT tools daily.

3.5 Mediataitojen tukena digitaalisessa arjessa (Strengthening multiliteracy) – Finland

Partner organisation

FSME is a non-governmental expert organisation dedicated to promoting and developing media education in Finland. As a national youth organisation, FSME aims to equip children and youth with essential media skills for societal participation and influence, while supporting their wellbeing in the everyday media environment. By addressing new media phenomena, FSME prepares young people for future media challenges. The organisation's activities are grounded in its core values: inclusion, equality, digital wellbeing, responsibility and education.

Intervention goals

This intervention, initiated and carried out by FSME, was conducted in partnership with Finnish vocational schools, with assistance from regional libraries in recruiting the schools. The primary objective was to develop teaching materials for vocational school students by testing them directly with students. Concurrently, the intervention aimed to enhance students' media literacy. Specifically, it sought to strengthen young people's versatile and flexible multiliteracy skills, including their interpretation and understanding of visual and audiovisual information, as well as critical literacy. The project also emphasised the significance of multiliteracy in everyday life, the workplace and societal participation.

Target group/vulnerability

The intervention was carried out in Finnish vocational schools, where students typically study between the ages of 16 and 19. While one of the main objectives was to develop teaching materials for vocational school students, the primary target audience and final beneficiaries were these students. They were prioritised because vocational schools had previously been less exposed to media and digital literacy activities, and there was a lack of materials to aid educators in these schools. A secondary target group included teachers and librarians who are potential users of the tested materials. This report presents findings based on data collected from the students.

Intervention format/activities

Intervention sessions lasted an average of 90 minutes. Each began with a short pre-survey that students completed on their mobile phones, designed to spark interest and prepare them for the topic. Guided by the FSME instructor, students then engaged in small group discussions. The first discussion focused on determining the trustworthiness of online messages and understanding the motivations behind them. Each student received a role card describing a person's identity, occupation and potential motives, which they used to evaluate trustworthiness. The second discussion revolved around a social media post where an influencer promoted a new diet. Students were asked to critically evaluate the various motivations behind such posts and identify who might benefit. Initial discussions took place in small groups, followed by a group-wide sharing of ideas. The instructor used visual aids, such as PowerPoint presentations, to facilitate the discussions.

3.5.1 Methodology

The intervention was implemented in the autumn of 2023 across six distinct groups in three vocational schools, with a total of 58 participants in the evaluation. Of these, 55 (95%) responded to the pre-survey and 53 (91%) the post-survey. To ensure anonymity, we combined pre- and post-surveys using nicknames created by the students. This proved challenging as some students did not attend class or refused to participate in the surveys or discussions. We do not have information on the total number of students that had been expected to participate on the intervention days.

Pre- and post-surveys were conducted online using the REDCap platform; respondent nicknames were used to connect the pre- and post-test results. Parts B and C were used in the pre-test and Parts A, B and C were used in the post-test (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Questionnaire application overview – FSME

To optimise the questionnaire’s length and avoid encroaching on the intervention’s content, extraneous questions were omitted. Identical wording and scales were used in both pre- and post-surveys to measure students’ media literacy and digital knowledge.

Sample: 55 out of 58 student participants (95%) responded to the pre-survey and 53 out of 58 (91%) to the post-survey.

Age and gender: respondents mean age according to their responses was 20.3, ranging between 16 and 54. There were 29 male students (51%), 22 female students (39%) and two non-binary students (3.6%). Two (3.6%) chose ‘Something else’ as their gender and two (3.6%) chose the ‘Prefer not to say’ option.

Educational background: Most of the participants were in full-time education (98.3%). Only two were also working part-time (3.4%). Primary school was the highest level of education for most (70%), and 26% reported that secondary school was their highest level of education (two preferred not to say).

3.5.2 Findings

Access

Out of 58 participants who responded to the post-survey, 42 (72%) reported having access to a computer, 53 (91%) to a smartphone, 4 (6.9%) to a tablet or eReader and 20 (35%) to a game consoles. Participants had more than two devices on average (mean = 2.1), and 20% of the sample reported to access the internet only from a smartphone.

Digital Literacy

Before the intervention, students rated their information navigation skills relatively high. Post-intervention, there were minor improvements in media literacy and digital knowledge, indicating that students already had a good foundational understanding.

Information navigation skills: This was only measured before the intervention. On a scale of 1–5 (‘Not at all true of me’ to ‘Very true of me’) participants perceived their information

navigation skills as 'Rather good' (mean = 4.1) before the intervention. The mean of the proportion of information navigation skills at a high level was 56%.

Media literacy and digital knowledge: Enhancing media literacy and digital knowledge were the main goals for this intervention. We did not notice a big change in participants' media literacy and digital knowledge, but the level of media literacy and digital knowledge was already 'Rather good' in the pre-survey.

Uses

For this intervention items related to health and wellbeing are interesting to reflect on, as part of the intervention's content was related to health-influencing social media.

Regarding health and wellbeing, there was a notable increase in participating students' intentions to use the internet and applications for fitness and health-related purposes after the intervention. Additionally, awareness of offensive content and unhealthy information online improved.

3.5.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Mainly based on digital knowledge questions, proportions estimated for digital skills were relatively similar between pre- and post-test, with 36% and 38% of correct answers, respectively.

Uses

This part included questions about use in informal learning, wellbeing, social and education activities. The dimension with the highest proportion of use was informal learning (92%), followed by social (80%), wellbeing (66%) and education (58%). As a result, participants reported having used the internet for 74% of the activities asked about in the survey.

Outcomes

Regarding outcomes, satisfaction with the results showed a different order from uses, with social activities as the dimension with the most people being happy with the results (93%), followed by education (83%), wellbeing (79%) and informal learning (67%). As a result, participants reported an overall achievement of 80% of the outcomes enquired.

3.5.4 Key insights

The FSME intervention organised for Finnish vocational school students increased students' intentions to use health-related apps and improved their awareness of harmful content, with instructor competence and materials being key factors for success. Before the intervention, students rated their information navigation skills highly. Post-intervention, there were minor improvements in media literacy and digital knowledge. The FSME intervention successfully engaged vocational students in critical discussions about digital information and its implications.

3.6 Hyvinvointialueen digipalvelut tutuiksi ikääntyneille (Digital wellbeing services pilot course for older people) – U3A Finland

Partner organisation

The University of the Third Age (U3A) an initiative in Jyväskylä University (JYU) is a university for elderly people, functioning as part of the Jyväskylä Summer University targeted at the general population. In U3A there are activities such as weekly lecture series, different seminars and courses, IT training and field trips for the general public (with no pressure over grades or performance). The U3A has organised digital skills training courses for elderly people for around five years with the same teachers. In 2023, the U3A teachers, together with a development project from the Centre of Excellence of Ageing and Care (CoE AgeCare) at the University of Jyväskylä, developed a new pilot course for the elderly together with various non-academic partners due to welfare service reorganisation in Finland. The non-academic partners and expert organisations involved in the pilot course development were the wellbeing services county of Central Finland, Jyväskylä Older People’s Council and the Finnish Association for the Welfare of Older People (Vanhustyön keskusliitto, VTKL). Steering groups formed from these expert bodies were included in the planning of the course content.

Intervention goals

In 2023, the focus of the course was set to specifically support elderly people’s use of the newly developed digital wellbeing services of the wellbeing services county of Central Finland and skills related to cybersecurity. In previous years a similar course had also been organised for the elderly but in a more general digital skills focus. In 2023, the course taught elderly people the key websites and tools for health support they can use in everyday life, such as a specific chat tool for senior citizens – ‘senior chat’ (other websites and tools include seniorisivut, hyvaks.fi, omaks.fi, hyvis.fi) and information security aspects related to digital service use at an everyday level (e.g., secure electronic authentication, security settings for devices).

Target group/vulnerability

The target group of the intervention and pilot course was elderly people living in Central Finland at retirement age. Elderly people in general can struggle with the constantly developing technologisation of society and health services. Therefore, organising digital courses and teaching for them must be planned carefully. Further, the teachers from the U3A were aware that the elderly participants usually do not enjoy being evaluated regarding their digital skills, and need a safe and calm environment to participate in learning digital skills.

Intervention format/activities

The course took place on 25 and 26 September 2023 at the University of Jyväskylä classroom, which was equipped with computers. On both days, the course taught the same content (with an estimate of 5.5 hours) by an experienced teacher from the U3A. The course had room for 14 participants per course day to secure a calm and participative learning environment. The

use of participants' own digital devices was encouraged during the course, but devices were also available from the U3A. The course also included four to five elderly peer tutors per course day who were advising participants with practical digital device and service/platform matters. The format of the course day included presentations by the teacher on the digital services and security aspects and learning how to use them on their own. The participants received a course handout that contained essential information about digital health services to be observed at home.

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3.6.1 Methodology

The quantitative pre-questionnaire data was collected at the beginning of each course day. Two researchers from the REMEDIS project's University of Jyväskylä (JYU) section attended the start of the course days, introduced the REMEDIS project and the questionnaire and all related issues of voluntary participation, anonymity and data protection of the research activities. The participants were given translated (Finnish) print forms of the pre-questionnaire (Parts A, B and C). During pre-questionnaire data collection, each participant was assigned an ID number, which made it possible to identify the pre- and post-questionnaire respondents afterwards, still securing their anonymity.

The post-questionnaires (Parts B and C) were sent to those respondents who gave their contact information (21) over a month after the course, mostly via email in digital form and some through print forms by post with pre-paid response envelopes attached. Most of the questions in the pre- (Parts A, B and C) and post-questionnaire (Parts B and C) were used. Questions regarding education and occupation (i.e., in education and unemployed) were not asked in the questionnaire as the content was not related to the lives of the participants (all were retired) (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Questionnaire application overview – U3A

U3A was the first to use the REMEDIS questionnaire. The questions and response options of the questionnaire were not exactly the same as those used in other countries as final adjustments to the questionnaire were made after the U3A intervention had been completed.

Sample

The response rate of the pre-test was 85%, as 22 out of the 26 course attendees filled out the pre-test questionnaire at the beginning of the course days. The mean age of the elderly respondents was 74, ranging from 68 to 81. One participant did not want to reveal their age. All the participants were retired; 18 were female and 4 were male. Over two-thirds of the sample had at least a university degree, and five reported having completed either primary or secondary education only.

The response rate of the post-test was 36%, as eight out of the 22 course participants who filled out the pre-test questionnaire at the beginning of the course days filled the post-test after a month. The mean age of the post-test respondents was 74, ranging from 68 to 77 . Hence, the post-test respondents did not include the oldest participants who answered the pre-test. Two post-test respondents were male (25%) and six were female (75%). Half the post-test respondents had completed some higher education level, two secondary school and the rest some other.

3.6.2 Findings

Since the post-questionnaire response rate was so low, the results are presented in many cases for three groups: the overall pre-test (i.e., pre-questionnaire Parts A, B and C) respondents, for those pre-test respondents who also responded to the post-test (i.e., post-questionnaire Parts B and C) and for the post-test respondents to be able to make more detailed comparisons between the pre- and post-test results.

Access

The questionnaire findings and qualitative findings further showed that there were quite varying digital skill levels among the participants. According to the questionnaire, most of the very few participants who answered the post-questionnaire a month after the course were somewhat more independent and up to date on what was happening, including use and skills of operating in digital environments.

Regarding access to the internet, all the pre- and post-test respondents had access to a computer or a smartphone, or other means to access the internet. Most had access to multiple devices (mean = 2.3), with three having access to a computer only and one to a smartphone only.

Digital Literacy

Regarding the technical and digital skills taught in the course, such as skills on how to protect a device or how to evaluate if online information could be trusted, the participants reported increased skill levels after the course, but mainly only among those participants who answered both the pre- and post-questionnaires. There were also indications of decreased skills, for example, to evaluate if a website could be trusted from the pre- to the post-questionnaire. This might have been because issues related to scamming people through fake websites to steal their banking or social security details provoked conversations on the course, and may have made some of the participants more aware and apprehensive of the security aspects of online services.

Concerning digital knowledge, the participants showed good awareness of internet search engines and browsing, which even increased from the start of the course to a month later. General social media skills (posting, liking, using hashtags and emojis etc.) among the participants were lower and did not increase after the course. The qualitative results also indicated that using specific social media types of tools, such as the senior chat, needs more emphasis and teaching time among elderly people.

Uses and outcomes

Overall, the participants were good at looking for information online and were happy with the results before, and especially after, the course. In particular, interest in and being content with looking up information on one's problems and health online had quite a large increase after the course. After the course, the participants were also overall better at judging health information online and reported more positively about digital technology. Still, the results indicate that online information on government or public service platforms and using them needs to be designed in ways that would be easier for elderly people to understand and use. This outcome also becomes evident from the qualitative results summarised, which indicate that various online health platforms and tools can be difficult for elderly people to use.

Digital health services can be challenging to adopt and use by elderly people, especially among those who have had less experience with technology or lack supporting networks to help with their use. The qualitative results point out many success factors related to elderly people's digital skills courses, such as including peer tutors, taking into account the varying digital skill levels of the participants, not including too much information for one teaching session (course day), and carefully considering research activities and their timing when evaluating the courses to be able to burden the course participants as little as possible.

3.6.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital Literacy

Participants obtained an overall score on digital skills at a high level of 20%. They reported having higher communication skills (31%), followed by technical (23%) and information (20%) skills. Last, participants reported comparatively lower content creation skills (9%).

Uses

In terms of internet use, participants reported primarily informal learning (82%) activities, followed by wellbeing and social activities (both at 75%), and finance, at 72%. Last, they reported a considerably lower proportion of work-related activities (14%).

In the post-test, participants reported a decrease in the overall proportion to 60%. This is due to reductions in the intention to use the internet for social (58%) and finance (44%) activities. However, informal learning (88%), wellbeing (79%) and work (31%) presented a relative improvement in future use intentions.

Outcomes

Participants reported having high levels of satisfaction with the outcomes obtained from their internet use, they were somewhat or very satisfied with 88% of the outcomes measured in the evaluation.. The specific proportions of outcomes they were satisfied with in each domain were: informal learning (87%), wellbeing (90%), social (93%), finance (89%) and work (100%).

Expected outcomes presented a slight overall decrease to 83%, and especially apparent in expected social outcomes (67%). The other domains, informal learning (79%), wellbeing (94%), finance (86%) and work (100%), presented relatively similar results.

3.6.4 Key insights

Elderly people have access to digital devices and the internet, but they have varying digital skill levels for using them. In course settings this can be addressed by hiring peer tutors, limiting course content and providing take-home information packages.

The pilot course succeeded in improving the participants' digital skills and ability to navigate information. After the course, the participants were more interested in searching for health-related information online. The course also enhanced the participants' ability to protect their devices and their awareness of cybersecurity issues. However, evaluating the reliability of websites was found to be slightly more challenging after the course.

3.7 Jak skutecznie uczyć seniorów korzystania z nowych technologii 'How to effectively teach seniors how to use new technologies' (TSOP) – Poland

Institutions with the potential for effective digital inclusion of seniors often lack professionally trained staff who can plan, implement and assess learning outcomes based on current pedagogical knowledge in geragogy, social gerontology and andragogy. This need has led to the development of an intervention aimed at training senior trainers.

Partner organisations

The partner organisation **Open UJ platform** was established in 2013 as part of the Jagiellonian University without Borders project, and presents both open educational resources (OER) and unlimited open online courses (massive open online courses, MOOC). Access to the courses is possible after creating an account. The Open UJ platform is part of the Teaching Support Centre at Jagiellonian University.

KIRE (Krakowski Instytut Rozwoju Edukacji) (Krakow Institute for the Development of Education) has been operating since 2008; it cooperates with 900 trainers and has an eLearning platform. A total of 45,000 people were trained there over 15 years.

The **National Federation of Associations of Universities of the Third Age** brings together Universities of the Third Age (U3A), which are non-governmental organisations that conduct active and continuous educational or activating activities for the elderly, or activities in the field of protecting the rights of the elderly, as part of their statutory tasks. The National Federation took honorary patronage over the intervention and provided support in reaching the target group.

The **Media Education Centre**, operating at Polish Radio Kielce, offers professional support in achieving educational goals in media education. **Super Senior Magazine**, the first magazine in Poland for the entire senior community, also provided support. Additionally, the cluster **Life Science Kraków Foundation** (Fundacja Klaster LifeScience Kraków), which offers access to an organised cooperation network within the scientific and business environment of the life science sector, was involved.

These three institutions provided media patronage for the intervention.

The Polish REMEDIS team at Jagiellonian University took the main role in developing the intervention addressed at senior trainers.

Intervention goals

The main goal of the intervention was to improve the methodological, didactic and digital competencies of trainers and caregivers of older adults. Equally important was the aim to create educational materials based on the recommendations developed in REMEDIS and make them openly accessible for trainers working with individuals needing support in enhancing their digital competencies. The activities focused on trainers of Polish seniors, a group that requires specialised support due to the unique challenges they face regarding digital inclusion and cybersecurity. A significant number of these trainers are also seniors themselves.

Target group

The intervention was developed as an eLearning course entitled: 'How to effectively teach seniors to use new technologies'. It was addressed at trainers and caregivers of older people. The motivation to participate in the course resulted primarily from the lack of knowledge about the phenomenon of the digital divide and the desire to improve their knowledge about seniors' teaching. Some participants treated the course as an element of their career path.

Intervention format/activities

Participation in the course was free of charge and only required creating an account on the Open UJ or KIRE platform (Moodle). Due to the participant being at the centre of designing activities, the eLearning course was placed on intuitive platforms with good technical support. The intervention was designed as an eLearning course based on recommendations resulting from REMEDIS analyses. The main goal was to provide senior trainers with knowledge on how to effectively teach this older group how to use new technologies. It consisted of nine modules/lessons: (1) digital exclusion; (2) digital competences; (3) specific educational needs of seniors; (4) supporting the learning process of seniors; (5) motivating seniors; (6) perfect geragogy; (7) rules facilitating the education of seniors in the field of digital competencies; (8) objectives and content of education; and (9) seniors safe on the internet.

3.7.1 Methodology

The eLearning course, 'How to effectively teach seniors to use new technologies', started on 1 February 2024. Data collection ended on 30 June 2024. The pre-test used Parts A, B and C of the REMEDIS questionnaire, with changes, such as adding questions regarding knowledge about the essence and causes of digital exclusion and the principles of teaching seniors. For the post-test, Part D of the questionnaire related to future uses and expected outcomes was applied (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Questionnaire application overview – TSOP

Sample: Out of 162 participants, 140 completed the pre-test, and of those who took part in the pre-test, 69 completed the post-test. We analysed the demographics of the 140 senior trainers who participated in the intervention (the eLearning course is available on two platforms), and we focused on and compared a subset of 69 individuals (49%) who completed pre- and post-intervention surveys. We also present data from a pre-test completed by 140 participants.

Age and gender: The average age of study participants who completed the pre- and post-test was 27 (range =19–55). Among the participants, 62 identified as women, 6 as men, and 1 identified differently.

Educational and professional background: Among the participants who completed the pre- and post-test, 46 people (67%) have secondary education, 11 (16%) have a Bachelor’s degree, and 11 (16%) have a Master’s degree.

Professionally, 46 people (67%) studied full-time and 1 (1%) part-time, 14 chose full-time education (23%), 2 chose part-time education (3%), and 1 was retired.

3.7.2 Findings

Access

A total of 139 participants (99%) reported using a smartphone that provides access to the internet or allows downloading applications; 136 declared using a computer (97%), 48 using a tablet or eBook reader such as an iPad or Kindle (34%), while 18 reported using a game console (13%). Therefore, most participants said they had access to multiple devices (mean = 2.4), with 2% of the sample only having access to a smartphone.

Digital Literacy

The participants in the course already had high digital skills, which can be seen in the results of the pre-test. For example, 44 respondents (31% of all those who completed the pre-test) answered that they knew how to create something that combines different digital media (e.g., photos, music, videos, GIFs). 54 (38%) answered in the pre-test that they knew how to edit existing digital images, music and videos. Regarding digital skills, for example, 106 (75%) answered in the pre-test that they knew how to use private browsing (e.g., the incognito mode).

Uses and outcomes

Compared to the pre-test, respondents improved their results on questions regarding ability to use advanced search engine functions and check website security. In the post-test, 26% (n = 18) indicated that after completing the course they now knew how to find high-quality information online in addition to 71% who already knew how to do it; 23% (n = 16) responded in the post-test that after the course they were able to avoid apps or websites that exposed them to harmful content, while 72% already knew how to do it.

3.7.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital Literacy

Regarding digital skills, participants had an overall score of 56% across all dimensions. The highest scores were for technical skills (75%), followed by communication (64%), information (47%) and content creation skills (38%). In the post-test, digital skills scores were calculated using responses to Part D, and as a result, the overall score was 75%.

Uses and outcomes

When participants were asked about uses, they had an overall score of 91% in the pre-test, with relatively high proportions in education (99%), work (97%) and informal learning (96%). The other three domains (i.e., finance, social and wellbeing) presented proportions of 86%,

86% and 81%, respectively. For the pre-test, the overall score was slightly higher at 95%, where future uses for education (99%), finance (99%), informal learning (98%) and social (98%) activities reported important improvements and a small decrease in the future use for work (91%) activities.

Outcome questions reported a pre-test overall score of 82%. The highest scores were for social and finance outcomes (93%), followed by work (82%), wellbeing (80%), informal learning (76%) and education (74%). In contrast, respondents reported expecting to achieve a high proportion of outcomes in the post-test, with an overall total of 97%. Wellbeing and social outcomes were the highest (99%), followed by education (98%), informal learning (97%), work (96%) and finance (93%).

3.7.4 Key insights

The intervention was addressed to a specific group that has a real impact on people at risk of digital exclusion. The entire intervention was designed as an eLearning course, which is available on two platforms, Open UJ and KIRE. It is free of charge and available to every user who creates an account on the platform.

In addressing the intervention to caregivers and trainers of older adults, the emphasis was primarily on teaching methods for seniors in using new technologies, as well as on knowledge related to improving the safety of older adults online.

The post-tests indicated that the course participants improved their skills. The topic of online safety proved to be particularly important. Respondents' answers in the tests, as well as in the open-ended questions, suggested that this issue requires special attention. Therefore, the recommendation for future interventions focused on digital inclusion is to incorporate online safety topics whenever possible.

3.8 Otwarty i kreatywny nauczyciel przyszłości 'The open-minded and creative teacher of the future' (OTF) – Poland

This intervention aims to enhance teachers' digital competencies. These activities were planned following an analysis of literature on the digitisation of education in European and global contexts (Tomczyk & Fedeli, 2022). Multilevel analyses identified gaps in the preparation of future teachers, highlighting the need to strengthen ML&DS and improve the application of ICT in teaching and learning. The intervention also seeks to modernise university curricula for developing digital competencies (Tomczyk, 2024), moving beyond the passive use of digital media and internet resources to actively creating digital teaching materials, with a focus on open educational resources (OER) (Cabero-Almenara *et al.*, 2023).

The organisation

The activities were carried out with the synergistic support of several institutions whose aim is to strengthen the quality of education in a broad sense. The Institute of Pedagogy at Jagiellonian University, within whose walls the intervention was implemented, played a special role in the activities. This was also due to the specificity of access to the research sample, that is, future and current teachers. In addition, a non-governmental organisation (NGO) of

practitioners, methodologists and researchers dealing with the issue of digitisation of education, that is, the Polish Society for Educational Technology and Media (Polskie Towarzystwo Technologii i Mediów Edukacyjnych), played a special role in the preparation and methodological support. Translation of the research tool as well as assistance in preparing detailed research reports for this intervention was provided by a representative of the partner organisation (included in the application form), that is, IH Bielsko-Biała.

Intervention goals

The initiative aims to enhance the digital and media competence of future teachers through the creation of OER. The aim is to shift their engagement from passive to active use of new media, thus strengthening their ability to develop modern ICT-based learning solutions. The project focuses on teachers undergoing pedagogical preparation in whom previous digital and media skills assessments have shown a need for specialised support. The initiative is part of the Polish team's emphasis on teacher training, and responds to the need to modernise education in the face of the challenges of the eLearning pandemic and crisis.

The project is expected to deliver the following benefits: increase the digital and media competence of future and in-service teachers; strengthen their ability to use new media in teaching; develop modern ICT-based educational solutions; improve the quality of teacher education; and modernise courses related to the application of ICT in education at Jagiellonian University.

Target group/vulnerability

The activities were targeted at two groups, namely future teachers and current teachers. The selection of the group was carried out in a purposeful way and resulted not only from the REMEDIS project objectives, but mainly in the need to strengthen ML&DS in the mentioned group. This task was dictated by: (1) the rapid sociotechnical changes in which ML&DS are key to increasing the effectiveness of learning and teaching (Stosic *et al.*, 2020); (2) the need to change the style of ICT use, in which teachers not only consume online content but also become active creators who prepare valuable teaching materials (Basgall *et al.*, 2023; Guillén-Gámez *et al.*, 2024); and (3) the low level of basic ML&DS, which translates into a style of using new media in the teaching process (Tomczyk, 2021). The selection of the group was also dictated by factors related to the methodological and empirical gap at the national level.

Intervention format

Designed to enhance media and digital skills, the course is divided into three stages: (1) Introduction to ICT; (2) Using and producing OER; and (3) Distribution (to be completed in the second half of 2024).

3.8.1 Methodology

The research was conducted between October 2023 and June 2024 using an online questionnaire (Microsoft Forms). The research consisted of two parts, namely a pre-test and a post-test. Teachers and prospective teachers completed the questionnaire before attending the computer lab and then attending the classroom course. The pre-test survey was completed by 108 participants and the post-test by 73. In addition to the general questions developed by the REMEDIS team, the tool included additional open-ended questions about the following content: What do you think was most valuable about the course and the creation of the video tutorials? What should be changed in the course? What elements should be added? Due to the extension of the project, it is also planned to continue the implementation process of the intervention in the academic year 2024/25. An overview of the questionnaire application is presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Questionnaire application overview – OTF

Sample

A total of 107 women and 1 man participated in the study. Of these, 47% held a Master’s or doctoral degree, while the rest were students (pre-service teachers). Participants were born between 1966 and 2005, with an average age of 30 (standard deviation: 10.8 years). Among the respondents, 56% were in full-time education, 27% were working full-time (at least 30 hours per week), and 7% were working part-time (8–29 hours per week).

Wellbeing

The majority of respondents felt they were able to work well. Most believed they were capable of learning effectively. Many expressed feeling overwhelmed and unable to keep up with current events. Overall, they tended to have a confident attitude. A significant number claimed to have good financial management skills. Respondents generally felt they had someone to

turn to for support when needed. There was a desire for more contact with family and friends. They felt capable of making conscious decisions about their health. Many pre-service and in-service teachers admitted to experiencing feelings of loneliness. They were aware of where to go to address various matters.

3.8.2 Findings

For this intervention there was data measuring the core indicators. However, this intervention was not set up around the REMEDIS core analytical framework and focussed on the design of a teacher tool rather than the impact of an ML&DS intervention on end beneficiaries everyday lives. Therefore, we do not discuss overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire separately and merged relevant findings into this general findings section.

Access

Respondents reported having access to multiple devices to access the internet, with each having access to two or three devices on average (mean = 2.5). Only a small proportion reported accessing the internet just from a smartphone (2.8%).

Considering the objectives of this intervention, the basic components of ML&DS were measured at the beginning of the mentioned process. The vast majority of the surveyed teachers rated their own media and digital competencies highly or very highly. Nevertheless, a trend can be observed that communication skills are at a much higher level than skills related to advanced information retrieval, assessing information credibility or editing and combining different types of material in digital form.

Digital Literacy

Technical and communication digital skills were highly scored among participants, 65% and 62% respectively, whereas information and content creation skills were comparatively lower, 37% and 34% respectively. Overall, the digital skills score was 50%. On the other hand, media literacy questions were correctly responded to in 69% of the cases.

Uses and outcomes

In the pre-test, participants reported having used the internet for 78% of the activities they were asked about. Informal learning had the highest score (95%), followed by finance (84%), social (80%), work (79%) and wellbeing (78%); formal education had the lowest score, at 51%.

Regarding outcomes, most participants reported being satisfied with the results obtained across all domains, with the highest results in finance (88%), followed by social (87%), work (86%), education (84%), wellbeing (72%) and informal learning (70%). The overall proportion related to outcomes was 81%.

When it comes to the post-test, the results regarding future use show a general improvement, with an overall score of 91%. Noteworthy, the score for education was 90%, which represents the highest increase in comparison to the pre-test. The only domain that reported a slight negative change was wellbeing, with a score of 75%. At the same time, 21% of participants declared not being interested in carrying out activities. Other activities were more popular for future use than they had been pre-intervention: social (98%), informal learning (97%), finance (96%) and work (90%). The results in expected outcomes also showed an overall increase, to 92%. Such positive changes in relation to the pre-test were observed for education (99%), work (99%), wellbeing (97%) and informal learning (89%), whereas slight decreases were found in finance (86%) and social (85%) domains.

Intervention-specific findings: course design evaluation

Overall, the course proved extremely valuable for participants, offering a wide range of new skills and experiences that directly enhanced their digital competencies. They learned to use programmes for data management and preparation, as well as tools for creating video tutorials, which significantly improved their daily work and preparation for their future careers. Participants appreciated the opportunity to test new tools like WeTransfer and selected edtech, which increased their confidence in using modern technologies.

The course also helped many break down barriers and step out of their comfort zones, especially regarding recording themselves and their voices. This experience taught them that complex technological tasks can become simpler with the right support and practice. High motivation to attend the course was driven by the need to adapt to the rapid digitalisation of education and the increasing expectations of teachers.

3.8.3 Key insights

Teachers rated their digital skills positively, especially in communication, although advanced information skills were weaker. While overall digital competency was moderate, media literacy performed better. Before the intervention, internet use was high for informal learning, but lower for formal education. After the course, future use and expected outcomes improved across most areas, especially in education. Participants found the course valuable, gaining confidence in using digital tools and overcoming challenges like recording themselves, while adapting to the increasing demands of digital education.

3.9 Cibermanagers para la Igualdad – Spain

Partner organisation

[PantallasAmigas](#) is an NGO founded in 2004 in Spain, aiming to defend and promote the rights of children and adolescents in the digital age by providing them with the skills and competencies needed for autonomous and positive online participation. With a global reach, PantallasAmigas has engaged in projects across different countries, particularly in Spanish-speaking regions, focusing on issues such as cyberbullying, sexting, sextortion, grooming and online security and privacy. Its five pillars of action include educational communication, digital life skills education, innovation, integration and the promotion of universal values. Among its actions, the *Cibermanagers para la Igualdad* (Cybermanagers for Equality) programme, initiated in 2010, is noteworthy for being the first intervention, in the Spanish context, to use peer and service learning methodologies to foster cyber-coexistence in schools and digital citizenship. Cybermanagers for Equality, an extension of Cibermanagers (2010), is funded by the Ministerio de Igualdad (Spanish Ministry of Equality), and was implemented for the first time in the academic year 2023–24 in different Spanish secondary schools, from Andalucía, Madrid, and Valencia to the Basque Country.

Intervention goals

The main goal of the programme is to address and prevent gender-based cyberviolence among minors in Spain, strengthening the training in key digital skills for the personal development of young people, as indicated by Spain’s Digital Agenda 2026. PantallasAmigas has implemented this programme in secondary schools, which are considered crucial venues for identifying and addressing such violence and promoting gender equality and positive coexistence online. The program is renewed annually, and it strives for sustainability and independence across schools, encouraging active student involvement. It transforms students into peer trainers and influencers using service learning, project-based learning and emotional design. Essential to the programme is the prior training of teachers in digital competencies and conflict resolution, tailored to student needs. This training enables teachers to effectively mediate and communicate digitally, respecting and responding to the specific needs of their students.

Target group/vulnerability

The primary target group is secondary school students (aged 13–16), particularly those from vulnerable backgrounds such as migrants, or those with low SES. Nonetheless, as addressed in d’Haenens *et al.* (2024), the motivation of the various stakeholders involved in the implementation of this programme (school centres, teachers, families, professionals and authorities from local and regional governments) has been the digital vulnerability of all secondary school students, stemming from a lack of critical thinking and digital skills, necessary to confront and overcome situations of risk or harm related to online coexistence and gender equality.

It is also important to address the fact that, due to barriers experienced in accessing our initial target group of vulnerable secondary students (see Martínez et al., 2023; d’Haenens *et al.*, 2024), the current sample cannot be considered vulnerable. While the participants may face other forms of digital and social challenges, the socioeconomic background of their families – characterised by high employment rates and relatively small family sizes – suggests a level of financial stability and modern family dynamics.

Intervention format/activities

Cibermanagers para la Igualdad is a dynamic eight-week training programme, free of charge. This no-cost availability necessitates a commitment from schools to foster positive digital coexistence, which includes training for teachers and active participation from students. Teachers volunteer for this programme, engaging in expert-guided, autonomous training that focuses on digital competence and the resolution of digital conflict among students and families. Likewise, students volunteer as cybermanagers, participating in training and content creation, and are dedicated to educating their younger peers and families.

Programme structure

The programme was distributed over four phases: Project introduction (Week 1); Teacher training (Weeks 1–4, voluntary training and a 4–6-hour online workshop); Student training (Weeks 4–7, teachers convey their knowledge to students volunteers, volunteer students develop their own content for future teaching of friends and family); and Action plan (Week 8, implementation and evaluation). Even though all the different phases are key to the successful development of the intervention, REMEDIS paid special attention to those phases that involve students’ participation, that is, weeks 6, 7 and 8.

3.9.1 Methodology

The evaluation process for the programme commenced in January 2024, following a year of co-development with PantallasAmigas (Martínez *et al.*, 2023).

The original quantitative tool used to evaluate this intervention was based on data collection through the ‘expected version’ pre-intervention test (Parts A, B and C) and post-intervention test (Parts A, B and D), as described by d’Haenens *et al.* (2024: 56–57). Intended for use across nine participating school centres, it focused particularly on five schools in a semi-rural municipality in Valencia, Spain, with many vulnerable students, including migrants and those from low SES backgrounds.

The pre-intervention questionnaire, adapted to the target group and intervention characteristics, was administered online via the Qualtrics platform. This format enabled efficient data collection. Each student received an anonymised ID to protect personal data. The pre-test was distributed in April, after week 5 of the training programme. Despite these efforts, only four questionnaires were completed by students from a semi-private school, not aligning with REMEDIS’ target group. The low response rate is attributed, among other issues (see d’Haenens, 2024: 42), to the innovative methodologies of the programme (implemented for the first time in Spain), which proved difficult for some teachers to assimilate due to their

limited time and heavy workload, hindering the tasks set by the REMEDIS project. As a result of this scenario, a new questionnaire was developed to evaluate the impact of this initiative after the intervention took place.

Following the results of the first round, the partner suggested that REMEDIS evaluate the impact of the intervention in two school centres located in a rural area in Cádiz (Andalucía). This area was particularly interesting because the initiative to join the programme was taken by the social educator of the local council, prompted by a report from a minor regarding a specific case of sexting and increased concern among families and children. The programme was implemented in school A by a tutor and in school B by the council's own educator. In school A, 28 cybermanagers (secondary school students) were recruited while in school B there were 15 cybermanagers. The questionnaire was administered online via the Qualtrics platform, and the link was sent to the adults in charge on 21 May 2024.

Students from school A completed the questionnaire on 22 May 2024, and students from school B completed it on 23 May 2024. School A provided digital devices for the students, while school B allowed some students to use their own devices due to an insufficient number of school devices. Two teachers supervised the students in both cases, and two REMEDIS researchers and the programme coordinator (partner) joined both sessions via Zoom.

Before starting, we informed the students about confidentiality, anonymity, the right to withdraw and the estimated length of the questionnaire (approximately 15 minutes). We also provided a brief explanation of the questionnaire's purpose, gave them the option to ask any questions, and clarified that it was not a self-evaluation. All students completed the questionnaire independently. The average time to complete the questionnaires was 17 minutes and 26 seconds, with some taking more than 30 minutes.

The questionnaire consisted of three parts: A (sociodemographic information) + B (questions related to the digital lived environment) + D (questions related to uses and outcomes). Part C was dropped as this evaluation does not include a pre-test. The outline of the data collection is presented in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Questionnaire application overview – Cybermanagers para la igualdad

Taking into account the characteristics of our target group (vulnerable minors) and the goals of the intervention, the three modules were adapted.

Part A (sociodemographics) questions related to education, occupation or work were removed because of the age (minors) of this target group. Instead, the changes prioritise understanding the students' socioeconomic conditions and family environment. By shifting the focus to family occupation, household composition and access to material goods, the changes try to provide a better understanding of the students' SES. Additionally, new questions were introduced to identify experiences of discrimination, which is crucial in understanding the challenges faced by vulnerable students.

The Part B (digital lived environment) question on media literacy was removed, as it was not directly relevant to the group or aligned with the goals of the Cibermanagers para la Igualdad initiative. In addition, the question regarding device usage was adapted to capture information about device ownership rather than just access. This change provides a clearer picture of students' digital autonomy, offering insights into their ability to navigate and use digital devices independently, and serves as a variable that contributes to understanding the SES of the participants, as owning personal devices can reflect the availability of material resources in the students' households.

Part D (uses and outcomes) questions, following the same approach as that in previous parts, with several questions related to wellbeing, work and finance, were dropped as they were not relevant to the students or the programme's goals. Key questions were adapted to focus on students' digital skills before and after the course, assessing progress in areas such as information navigation, social interaction and education, and by taking into account that we could not assess this group with a pre-test. New questions were also added to evaluate the impact of the programme on students' identity and learning outcomes, aligning with the initiative's objectives and the specific characteristics of the target group.

The students' feedback regarding the questionnaire was positive. They found the questions easy to answer and none made them feel uncomfortable or judged. Most stated that they could express themselves freely as they knew that it was anonymous.

Sample

The sample for the programme primarily consisted of 15- to 16-year-olds, with a balanced gender distribution (20 boys, 19 girls). Most participants' parents were employed, indicating financial stability and modern family roles, with minimal dependence on traditional single-income models. Family composition data reveals that 27 students had one sibling, suggesting relatively small family units that may support individualised parental attention. Overall, these demographics suggest that the participants were not from low SES backgrounds or vulnerable family situations.

Indicators of vulnerability

The questionnaire included two additional questions that asked students about their access to certain material goods and also about potential feelings of discrimination and the reasons for this. These two questions add important information about potential socioeconomic or culturally vulnerability.

Results show that most students have access to everyday material goods. Nonetheless, some insufficiencies were noted among the course participants. Specifically, four students reported not having enough money for field trips and school activities, and five did not have pocket money. Additionally, two students did not have internet access at home. Regarding feelings of discrimination, a small percentage of students admitted to various negative experiences: three felt inferior to their peers and believed others were treated better, three felt that people thought they were not smart, and five believed others thought they were better than them. Additionally, three reported being called names or insulted by other children. However, none of the students attributed these feelings of discrimination to factors such as family origins, skin colour, religion or financial status.

Problem-solving skills (wellbeing)

Regarding problem-solving skills and overall wellbeing, most students demonstrated high confidence ('Very true of me'). Specifically, 39 individuals reported they could participate well in class, 32 considered themselves generally confident and 36 had someone they could call for support when needed. However, for some students their level of wellbeing was lower: 15 would like more support from family and friends, 9 felt behind what was happening in the world and 3 tended to feel lonely.

3.9.2 Findings

The evaluation of this intervention included a quantitative part in which 41 secondary school students from two different schools located in a rural area from Cádiz (Andalucía) participated. These students, also recognised as cybermanagers (n = 40), completed a post-test questionnaire. The results, based on the answers to parts A, B and D, referred to sociodemographic information, digital lived environment and uses and outcomes of the intervention, respectively. The qualitative part of the evaluation is mainly based on the results of two personal interviews (online) with the two adults (n = 2) in charge of leading both groups (school teacher and social educator from the local council). The main findings are as follows.

Access

Results show that most students have access to everyday material goods. Nonetheless, some insufficiencies were noted among the course participants. Specifically, four students reported not having enough money for field trips and school activities, and five did not have pocket money. Additionally, two students did not have internet access at home. Among the participants, 16 had their own computer (desktop or laptop), while 20 shared one. Additionally, 37 owned a smartphone that provided internet access, with only 1 person sharing it. Regarding tablets or eReaders, 28 owned one, while 6 shared them. Furthermore, 19 had their own game console, and 9 shared it.

Digital Literacy

Overall, participants demonstrated strong digital skills in communication and interaction, as well as technical and operational skills. While students are generally capable of creating and editing digital content, there is a need for better content dissemination skills, which are essential for successfully reaching the programme's goals. The most significant area for improvement is information navigation and processing, suggesting these skills were not sufficiently addressed. Enhancing media literacy is crucial to achieving the programme's goals and ensuring students can effectively evaluate and trust online information.

There are significant areas for improvement in digital knowledge in this programme. Students need a better understanding of content creation and production, greater awareness of social media influences, and an improved understanding of information navigation and processing. These findings are aligned with the qualitative results.

Communication and interaction skills were the most prevalent among participants, with 38 proficient in choosing the appropriate communication tool for various situations. Additionally, 37 knew what images and information were appropriate to share online, and 36 understood when to use emoticons, text speak or capital letters.

Technical and operational skills were also well-developed, with more than 38 participants able to protect a device using methods like a PIN, screen pattern, fingerprint or facial recognition. However, only 32 were knowledgeable about using private browsing, and 30 knew how to store files on the iCloud.

In contrast, content creation and production skills were somewhat less widespread: while 33 participants could create content combining different digital media and 30 knew how to edit existing digital content, only 20 knew how to ensure their online posts reached a wide audience.

Information navigation and processing skills were the least developed. Only 16 were able to verify the truthfulness of online information, and 20 could assess the trustworthiness of websites. Additionally, just half knew how to make their online posts widely visible.

Digital knowledge

When asked about their digital knowledge, the results indicated that content creation and production had the lowest proficiency rates. Only 17 participants correctly disagreed that the first search result was always the best information source, and just 10 correctly identified that the first post seen on social media was not necessarily the latest post by a contact.

In terms of communication and interaction, 15 participants knew that companies paid ordinary people to promote their products in videos and content they created, and 18 understood that

likes or shares on social media could have negative impacts. In the information navigation and processing category, 26 participants demonstrated a good understanding that using hashtags increased the visibility of a post. However, only half correctly recognised that search results were personalised and not the same for everyone.

Uses and outcomes

Students are now more likely to seek information online but tend not to seek differing opinions, highlighting a need for improvement in exploring diverse perspectives. Additionally, both quantitative and qualitative results suggest that further enhancement in media literacy (ML) is needed to increase students' confidence and skills in finding quality information and avoiding fake news.

Regarding educational uses of the internet, the programme seems to have a positive impact on students. Most plan to seek study materials online, and some intend to enrol in similar courses. However, areas for improvement include ensuring more students avoid missing out on digital learning opportunities, better navigating collaboration platforms and using the internet to enhance school performance.

Post-intervention findings from programme reveal important impacts on students' digital experiences. Regarding their engagement in information-seeking activities online, 28 indicated they would definitely look up information online to answer their questions in the coming months, although only 7 would seek information that presents different opinions to their own. Concerning the impact that the programme had on their ability to assess information quality, 7 stated that now that they are cybermanagers they can manage to find quality information on things that they are interested in, and 15 can now manage to avoid being misled by fake news or misleading information online.

Social activities (digital communication intentions and anti-bullying actions)

As to social activities such as digital communication intentions, 33 participants declared their intentions to use the internet to communicate with family and friends in the coming months. They also intended to use the internet to get in touch with other people to solve any problems related to cultural or youth activities, public services or public transport (n = 15). Regarding anti-bullying actions, 15 participants expressed that since becoming cybermanagers they would take positive action if they or someone they know was being harassed or bullied online, and 14 intended to engage in productive discussions around social issues on the internet or mobile apps.

Educational impact

With respect to educational uses, the majority of the participants (n = 25) said they would definitely use the internet in the following months to find study materials that they wouldn't be able to find at school or the library. Furthermore, 9 confirmed they would sign up for other

courses online similar to Cibermanagers para la Igualdad. It is also remarkable that in terms of educational impact, 15 stated that since becoming cybermanagers they would avoid missing out on digital learning opportunities such as the programme Cibermanagers para la Igualdad; six recognised that they could better navigate different platforms used for collaboration, and five stated that the internet would now improve their school performance.

Intervention-specific findings

Regarding feelings of discrimination, a small percentage admitted to various negative experiences: 8% felt inferior to their peers and believed others were treated better, 8% felt that people thought they were not smart, and 12% believed others thought they were better than them. Additionally, 8% reported being called names or insulted by other children. However, none of the students attributed these feelings of discrimination to factors such as family origin, skin colour, religion or financial status.

The programme seems to have a positive impact on students' digital communication and social activities. Quantitative results show that most plan to communicate with family and friends online, and some aim to solve issues related to cultural activities and public services. However, the students' answers show that **there is a need for more proactive anti-bullying actions and greater engagement in social issue discussions**. These results are aligned with the qualitative results and may indicate areas for further improvement.

Post-programme, students intend to use the internet to explore gender differences, ethnic groups, identity-related opinions and sexual orientations. Nonetheless, the relatively low engagement in these areas suggests **a need for further enhancement in ML&DS in order for them to seek diverse perspectives and deeper online engagement with these topics**.

The programme has positively impacted students' digital skills to challenge gender inequality and engage in diverse online conversations related to this topic. They are able to identify various forms of online violence, gender-based violence in social networks or video games and societal image stereotypes in online content. However, the programme did not have much impact on developing skills for **engaging with people from different backgrounds or questioning opinions (online) about their identity**.

3.9.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital Literacy

Overall, participants had a score of 51% of skills at a high level. Regarding specific categories of digital skills, scores were, from higher to lower, technical and operational (63%), communication (56%), content creation (48%) and information (38%).

Uses

The post-test enquired about informal learning, social and education activities online. Participants reported having done 88% of the activities enquired about. Informal learning had the highest proportion, at 91%, followed by education (86%) and social (85%) activities.

Outcomes

Expected outcomes presented a similar pattern to use, with participants reporting high levels of satisfaction with the results in informal learning (85%), social (82%) and education (83%) domains. Overall respondents were satisfied with 83% of outcomes of their internet use across all domains.

3.9.4 Key insights

The results of the programme reveal both strengths and areas for improvement in students' ML&DS. It has positively impacted students' digital communication and problem-solving skills, with many demonstrating confidence in engaging in online interactions. The programme also increased awareness of gender differences and online violence, helping students recognise gender-based violence and stereotypes in digital spaces. These outcomes reflect the programme's success in promoting essential digital skills and social awareness among students. However, there are areas that need improvement. Media literacy, particularly in content dissemination and information navigation, remains a challenge for many students. They also require more support in critically evaluating online information and seeking diverse perspectives.

To enhance the effectiveness of the programme, a focus is recommended on improving students' ML&DS, particularly in the areas of information navigation, content dissemination and critical evaluation of online information. Emphasising these skills will empower students to better understand and engage with topics related to gender discrimination and violence against women. Additionally, fostering an environment that encourages seeking diverse perspectives and deeper online engagement with social issues will further enhance their ability to recognise and challenge various forms of online violence and gender-based stereotypes. By addressing these areas, the programme can more effectively equip students with the necessary skills to navigate and counteract digital and social challenges related to gender inequality that will benefit their wellbeing.

3.10 Desfake – Spain

Partner organisation

Verificat is a non-profit organisation based in Catalonia, founded in 2019 as the first Catalan fact-checking platform, and formally established in 2020 during the Covid-19 pandemic, responding to the urgent need to address scientific misinformation. Verificat joined the REMEDIS consortium at the end of April 2024. Its primary objective is to counteract disinformation and promote media and information literacy (MIL) (*alfabetización mediática*

informativa, AMI) through journalism and education, fostering a more informed and critical society. It aims to enhance critical thinking among the public, particularly amongst young people, by equipping them with the skills to discern truthful information from fake information.

Verificat has several lines of action in the educational and training context. Nonetheless, their leading initiative is the project Desfake, launched in 2020. Desfake is an educational programme aimed at secondary schools. It started as a pilot project and has evolved into a transformative initiative for educational centres. It is based on a didactic methodology and a series of resources focused on MIL, seeking to mitigate disinformation in secondary schools.

Verificat is an independent entity that maintains a neutral and impartial approach in all its topics and activities. All its content is reviewed by at least three team members to ensure quality and a plurality of viewpoints. Its impartiality is certified by the International Fact-Checking Network, whose code of principles it has signed. Verificat’s team is neutral, independent and committed to transparency, promoting gender equality and young talent. It receives both public and private funding, ensuring that its funders do not interfere with its editorial processes.

Intervention goals

The primary goal of Desfake is to foster critical thinking in students by enhancing their MIL. It aims to help students critically interpret and engage with the information they consume and produce. It began as a pilot at LLOR school in Sant Boi de Llobregat, and later expanded to include additional schools in Catalonia. The project focuses on fostering critical thinking and transforming educational practices related to MIL. The programme is supported by various educational and governmental bodies, emphasising its significant role in combating misinformation.

Initially targeting secondary education, Desfake has expanded to include primary education, focusing on fifth and sixth graders. It collaborates with teachers and educational entities to integrate MIL into the curriculum, using interactive methods such as TikTok videos to engage students. Starting as a pilot, it aims to transform educational centres into MIL hubs. Desfake supports vulnerable students, ensures inclusivity and continuously evolves based on feedback, with support from various educational and governmental bodies and collaboration with entities like Escuela21.

Target group/vulnerability

The recent incorporation of this partner into the REMEDIS consortium has led to a co-development phase, during which the target group and specific initiative for co-evaluation among the three Desfake initiatives was co-designed. While previous work (d’Haenens *et al.*, 2024) primarily targeted vulnerable secondary school students, this approach has shifted. In this section, we present the rationale for selecting the target group we co-evaluated with Verificat, from June until October 2024.

Verificat's priority regarding the Desfake programmes is to implement them in high-complexity schools, characterised by several socioeconomic and educational factors such as families with low SES, high rates of unemployment, migratory backgrounds, special education needs or disadvantaged geographic areas. Apart from this, it always considers vulnerable secondary and primary school students are the target group of its interventions, but vulnerable students are not always the primary target group.

REMEDIIS co-evaluated the *Desfake Face-to-Face (presenciales Desfake)* programme with the partner organisation. The primary target group comprised secondary school teachers in high-complexity schools in Catalonia. While this group is not strictly considered vulnerable, the schools where they teach are classified as vulnerable, as is the secondary target group of this programme: vulnerable secondary school students attending high-complexity schools in the Catalanian area.

Intervention format/activities

The Desfake project, which is based on a didactic methodology and a series of resources to promote MIL, is being implemented in three distinct programmes. The first is *Desfake Centres (centros Desfake)*, a pilot project that Verificat is attempting to extend into the 2024–25 academic year. It involves 30 hours of training (largely online and autonomous) for a team of three to five teachers within an educational centre, along with guidance from Verificat. The goal is not only to provide training but also to transform the way MIL is approached within the centre.

The second programme is *Desfake Face-to-Face (presenciales Desfake)*, which involves a 4-hour session with the Verificat team and students, after which the teachers lead a classroom project with the students. The continuation of this module for the next academic year is uncertain.

The third programme is the *Desfake Teachers (docentes Desfake)* model, an innovative and comprehensive online training programme designed to enhance teachers' digital competence and media literacy skills in order for them to transmit it to their students. The programme is structured to be flexible, with training hours ranging from 15 to 30 hours, allowing teachers to complete it at their own pace. The training format includes asynchronous modules featuring engaging educational capsules and interactive activities, all aimed at developing critical analysis skills in digital content. Teachers participating in the programme benefit from a wide range of materials, including a resource library with articles, videos, case studies and best practice guides. The training content, carefully developed by Verificat, is current, relevant and aligned with best practice in MIL education. Verificat also provides continuous support throughout the training process, offering guidance, answering questions and facilitating discussions to enhance the learning experience. On completion, teachers can receive official certification, acknowledging their enhanced digital competencies.

The module which REMEDIIS chose for co-evaluation is *Desfake Face-to-Face*.

Between October and December 2024, a pilot project is scheduled to be conducted in three secondary schools in Barcelona, with the possibility of including a fourth school. The estimated length of the implementation is approximately 4 to 5 weeks per school.

The project structure is organised into three main phases:

1. **Initial kick-off (4 hours):** At the start of each implementation, the Verificat team, composed of professionals (not volunteers) with prior training in the subject matter, provides 4 hours of training to the teachers who have chosen to participate in the project. As this training is face-to-face and in the school centre, all the teachers can participate in this training, even though they won't implement it in the classroom. In this kick-off session, the objectives, methodology and necessary resources for the activities are presented.
2. **Teacher-led implementation:** In the following weeks, the teachers are responsible for implementing the project activities in the secondary school classrooms, focusing on information verification work with the students. In the first school, four teachers participate, in the second school, two teachers and in the third school, three teachers.

During this phase Verificat also provides continuous support, offering guidance to the teachers to access materials, answering questions regarding the content or the implementation process, and facilitating discussions to enhance the learning experience.

3. **Closure and feedback (2 hours):** At the end of the project, the Verificat team returns to the school for a 2-hour closing session. During this phase, feedback from teachers and students is provided on the verifications carried out by the students, and the results are jointly evaluated (internal evaluation by Verificat through discussions with teachers and students).

3.10.1 Methodology

The *Desfake Face-to-Face* programme, co-evaluated by REMEDIS and the partner organisation, used planned evaluation methods including both qualitative and quantitative methodologies.

The qualitative part focuses on interviews with at least two teachers who received the training and implemented the programme in the classroom with secondary school students.

The quantitative part will follow the REMEDIS 'best case scenario' data collection model (d'Haenens *et al.*, 2024), dividing the questionnaires (pre- and post-test) between teachers who participated in 4 hours of training (face-to-face) delivered by Verificat and implemented the programme in the classroom with students (4/5 weeks), and the students who receive this training from the teachers.

3.10.2 Findings

Verificat has already implemented evaluation strategies (based on qualitative and quantitative techniques) in the *Desfake Centres* programme seeking to understand the programme's broader impacts, such as identity, inclusion and digital knowledge. The evaluation was conducted through questionnaires, interviews and focus groups involving the entire educational community, allowing for the identification of strengths and areas for improvement. The results highlight the high quality of the materials, which inspired new teaching methodologies as well as the person-centred methodology. The project meets teachers' training needs in MIL, providing tools and resources to empower teachers and students. However, the teaching staff noted the need for more time to explore the resources. D'Haenens *et al.* (2024) detail how Verificat has encountered some challenges in evaluating the *Desfake Centres* programme due to resource constraints, limited time and staff availability, combined with substantial teachers' workloads.

This prior evaluation framework and the results represented key material for REMEDIS in order to develop an evaluation method adapted to the *Desfake Face-to-Face* model mainly focused on secondary school teachers and students as beneficiaries, as well as to its programme characteristics in order to measure tangible outcomes for all end beneficiaries.

Qualitative part

The minimum requirement is to conduct at least two interviews with the beneficiaries (teachers). These will be online or face-to-face, depending on the availability of the beneficiaries. The interview script will be based on REMEDIS' facilitation canvas (see Martínez *et al.*, 2023; d'Haenens *et al.*, 2024), addressing their point of view regarding the objectives of the programme, access and resources, motivations to join this training and ML&DS addressed. The interviews will be focused on the barriers they observe, and the impact and outcomes that the intervention can have on their teaching quality, their students' learning, and on the families and the school community.

Quantitative part

The quantitative part will be focused on REMEDIS' 'best case scenario' data collection model (d'Haenens *et al.*, 2024), by providing the questionnaires to teachers who received the training from Verificat and implement the programme with students (for 4/5 weeks), and also to those students who receive that training from teachers. The main data collection activities are as follows:

- **Pre-questionnaire with Parts A, B and C** that will be applied before the 4 hours of face-to-face teacher training starts. Considering that this training can incorporate teachers in groups (same school centre) or individually, this pre-test will have an online format. The questionnaire, developed by REMEDIS researchers, will be supervised by the partner to make sure that it fits with the beneficiaries' characteristics as well as with the content, objectives and goals of the programme. New questions, related to MIL, will be included, as suggested by the partner during the co-evaluation process.

- After the face-to-face training delivered by Verificat and once the programme has been implemented in the classroom (4/5 weeks), a **post-test questionnaire** (online) with Part D will be applied to these same teachers.
- After one month of having received the training, a **follow-up**, similar to the pre-intervention one, in order to identify how skills, literacy, use and perceived outcomes have changed over time, will be applied (online).

REMEDIS and Verificat’s intention is to implement a questionnaire (pre- and post-test) for students who receive training from the teachers. Nonetheless, this will depend on the teachers’ availability to distribute the questionnaires among students and supervise and guide them during their completion. The questionnaires implemented will be subject to modifications to respond to the intervention’s specific needs.

Since the core REMEDIS evaluation questionnaire has not yet been implemented pre- and post-intervention no overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire are discussed in this section.

3.10.3 Key insights

The evaluation of the *Desfake Face-to-Face* programme aims to address the barriers identified during the co-evaluation phase to establish a robust method for effectively measuring the programme’s positive outcomes. The detected barriers include a lack of control over how and when the pre- and post-intervention questionnaires are administered, the need to provide teachers with more time to explore and utilise the resources and materials, and reluctance from some teachers to participate in comprehensive evaluations due to concerns about additional workload and the perception of being assessed.

By implementing a structured and systematic evaluation model, adapted to the characteristics of both primary and secondary beneficiaries (teachers and students) as well as to the training programme, it is expected to obtain a comprehensive and reliable understanding of the programme’s effectiveness. This model will measure improvements in teachers’ ML&DS and MIL competencies, both in the short and long term. The goal is to ensure the successful and sustainable implementation of the programme in high-complexity schools in the Catalanian area.

3.11 Citizens Online (CO) – UK

Partner organisation

Citizens Online is a non-profit charitable organisation aimed at promoting digital inclusion across the UK. It is mostly funded by local authorities to support people seeking jobs and trying to use online services such as online shopping or applying for Universal Credit (a state benefit).

Intervention goals

One-to-one support sessions aim to increase people’s confidence in using the internet to engage in more varied uses that may lead to better employment and education opportunities.

In that sense, the long-term expected outcome is helping people to upskill in order to increase their income and quality of life. A secondary service is to help people access devices such as tablets or laptops, and to apply for free data plans offered by telecom companies.

During the project, Citizens Online merged with AbilityNet, another charity working on digital inclusion focused on people with disabilities or special accessibility requirements. According to the partners in Citizens Online, the merger will mean an expansion of expertise and reach of the work done by Citizens Online to other areas.

Target group/vulnerability

Citizens Online is focused on training individuals in digital skills for daily activities and increasing their chances of finding jobs or educational opportunities. The learners come from a range of backgrounds, but include the long-term unemployed, individuals with a disability, benefits recipients, migrants and other groups who may need support to be able to fully participate in a digital society.

Intervention format/activities

Citizens Online’s different initiatives use a similar approach. It recruits and trains volunteer digital champions, explaining to them what digital exclusion is and how they could help learners to achieve better skill levels. It does not follow a specific curriculum during the one-to-one sessions, but the activities are adapted to learners’ needs. In addition, it provides devices and data plans, if required. It offers specific timeslots every week and learners can schedule a meeting or attend drop-in sessions. Based on comments left by participants, some have made use of the one-to-one support for years, relying on it for all internet-related tasks, and others attend sessions to solve one problem they have and do not then come back.

3.11.1 Methodology

The questionnaire used to evaluate the intervention built on the one used already by Citizens Online to measure learners’ satisfaction. The questions were focused on measuring confidence in key activities and asking how the service could be improved. Therefore, Citizens Online decided to reframe some questions based on the REMEDIS questionnaire that were of interest, especially those related to work.

Citizens Online asked about confidence in undertaking specific activities they presumed their users were most likely to do online. The ten items include six questions on general activities, such as using web browsers to find information, using messaging apps to communicate with family and friends, and using the internet to access digital services such as household accounts, benefits or medical appointments. The four remaining items asked about activities related to work, such as creating CVs online or applying for jobs online.

Another section of the questionnaire focused on measuring how support increased their chances of finding jobs, for instance whether they used the internet to find and apply for jobs, update their CV or create profiles on digital platforms. Based on the REMEDIS questionnaire Parts C and D related to work, Citizens Online explored if participants were able to undertake

certain job-seeking activities, and if so, whether this was due to what they learned during the intervention or because they already knew how to do it.

A third section of the questionnaire explored what other activities in general participants were able to do after they attended the one-to-one or group sessions. Activities asked about included formal and informal relations (e.g., connect with family and friends, access to welfare benefits), finance (e.g., online shopping or banking) and health (access to GP services or leisure activities). In addition, the questionnaire asked about sociodemographics, what kinds of services from Citizens Online they used (e.g., one-to-one support, devices, data plans) and how they rated such support, as well as several open questions.

Data collection took place in two particular projects, namely Digital Gwynedd (North Wales) and Digital Brighton & Hove (South East England). Questionnaires were filled out by participants with the support of voluntary digital champions.

The proposed questionnaire, including relevant questions for Citizens Online not included in the original REMEDIS questionnaire, was applied post-intervention, using Parts A, B and D (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Questionnaire application outline – Citizens Online

Sample: The sample consisted of 18 participants who completed the questionnaire between January and May 2024. Questions related to confidence in doing job-seeking activities were asked only of those who attended sessions to receive support in applying for jobs.

Age: Citizens Online used age intervals to collect age categories ranging in 10-year steps from the age of 25. Nine of the respondents were 65 or over. Four participants were between 55 and 65, and only one person was in the other intervals: 25–34, 35–44 and 45–54.

Gender: Among those who reported gender (n = 16), the great majority were female (n = 14) and only two were male.

3.11.2 Findings

Citizens Online used very different questionnaires from the ones designed by REMEDIS for comparisons, and so general findings are discussed below with reference to general survey sections, but not specific questionnaire items. The questionnaire based on the REMEDIS instrument will be applied from November 2024 until early 2025. Since the instrument applied

by CO differed substantially from the one proposed by REMEDIS, this section does not include an overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire section.

Access

Ten respondents reported getting support by receiving donated devices (e.g., tablets or laptops), and among those, five also received data sim cards. Therefore, even when the primary role of Citizens Online is the provision of training, a meaningful proportion of learners need support in relation to access, which represents one of the first barriers for engagement.

One of the participants said that even though she already had a smartphone, completing CVs on that device was exhausting, so having received a laptop to work on preparing a CV allowed her to save time and increase her opportunities by applying for more jobs.

In addition, it was difficult for participants to access the interventions in rural locations, because inconvenient public transport options made it difficult to commute. Therefore, the digital champion in North Wales chose to go and visit learners where they were, which overcame an important barrier to participating in these interventions.

Confidence and skills

Means were calculated for confidence-related questions for each, and an increase in confidence levels after the one-to-one sessions was found in most cases.

The group of older adults (65 or over) were more interested in the support for online browsing and leisure activities; as a consequence, no increase in confidence was observed when they were asked about confidence to perform work-related activities.

A lack of confidence is not only an issue for elderly people who have been less exposed to technology. The open-ended questions indicated that there were participants who were familiar with using the internet for certain purposes, but they preferred to do the first steps guided by digital champions since new activities had grabbed their attention, and they felt uncomfortable taking on these unexplored areas on their own. One participant who reported being a healthcare professional expressed that she wanted to learn how to make electronic music, but since she had not done this before, she preferred to ask a digital champion for help.

Uses (activities)

Participants were asked if the support received helped them perform a range of activities. In addition to work-related activities, a contribution to informal social relations and personal wellbeing was identified through the questionnaire. In contrast, more instrumental activities related to finance or accessing GP services seem not to have improved for many participants.

Findings specific to the intervention

Even though providing devices was regarded as a secondary service, the opportunity of provision of devices and data plans was taken up by half the participants who responded to the questionnaire. It became clear that how successful they could be in getting a job (an

important outcome indicator for Citizens Online) not only depended on the quality of the support but also on having quality access.

External conditions were also likely to affect the relative success of interventions. The availability of jobs in rural areas of North Wales is different from that in Brighton & Hove, an urbanised area in South East England with easy access to London. These external factors could not be controlled by the intervention, but cannot be ignored.

Participants in North Wales highlighted the value of the digital champion in providing support by travelling in his vehicle to meet them, to avoid limited public transport infrastructure becoming a reason for not attending sessions.

These elements require further exploration with adequate instruments and a larger sample that would permit Citizens Online to collect better evidence of the impact of their interventions. A good balance between comprehensive instruments and reasonable length must be struck. Desirable more lengthy questionnaires are unlikely to be completed, and could negatively impact the results of the intervention if a large proportion of time has to be used for data collection.

3.11.3 Key insights

The initial exploratory analysis from data collected from Citizens Online underscores the importance of exploring different outcomes even when some of the interventions are focused on work-related activities online. The importance of having adequate devices was highlighted in preliminary enquiries.

One of the main reasons, explicit or not, for local authorities to hire the services of Citizens Online is to improve people's opportunities to secure jobs. However, based on participants' comments and uses after support, they are also interested in diversifying their activities online and improving their lives in terms of their social and personal wellbeing. Therefore, it seems that the extended collateral benefits of the programme were not properly evaluated, and the impact of the intervention in other domains was underestimated.

3.12 CodeYourFuture (CYF) – UK

Partner organisation

CodeYourFuture (CYF) is a charity focused on training people of low-income status in software development to find better job opportunities. The Digital Literacy Programme (DLP) was launched in 2022 to cover the essential digital skills needed for day-to-day activities, given that some applicants did not even have a basic level to start with the introduction to programming. After a few cohorts, CYF realised that a great proportion of adults registered for the course were not interested in the training as part of a process to become developers, but rather in having the basic skills to use, for example, email, banking or navigation apps.

Target group/vulnerability

The course is offered to all adults and is free. In line with CYF’s other training offer, the DLP prioritises people from low-income backgrounds, and refugees and asylum seekers in particular. Most participants in the course have been born overseas, and their mastery of the English language was a barrier to accessing jobs, education and a social life, so some activities focus on using translation applications, understanding what job-seeking digital platforms are used locally, and further training opportunities they could apply for.

Intervention goals

Trainers teach learners how to search for information using search engines, manage their email communications according to the people they are interacting with (netiquette), use an office suite to create and edit online CVs, and how to access online banking and basic guidance to stay safe online. By developing these skills, CYF aims to facilitate the integration of participants into a digital society and prevent social isolation due to a lack of digital skills and knowledge.

Intervention format/activities

The intervention is a three-week in-person course, usually taking place on Saturdays, with an estimated length of 5 hours per session. A lead trainer introduces the content and explains activities to be done in class, while other trainers support participants on an individual basis. The course is run in different places in the UK, but the data collected corresponds to two cohorts in London in March and April 2024. Each session comprises activities led by CYF volunteers, as well as individual and group work.

3.12.1 Methodology

The base questionnaire of the REMEDIS project was used with former participants of the DLP course between January and February 2024. Cognitive interviews were carried out, exploring what participants understood in each question, and contrasting such assumptions with the purpose of the questions from the project side. English and Spanish language versions were used since some of the interviewees participated in a course delivered in Spanish for a charity working with Latino immigrants.

The data collection was carried out during the first and last sessions of the course and was supported by CYF staff and volunteers. They agreed to use the instrument as proposed by the REMEDIS team, so no changes were made to the base questionnaire. A pre- and post-test were applied for two cohorts in March and April 2024. The pre-test was applied in the first session after students signed up. The post-test was applied after the final assessment.

The online platform Qualtrics was used to apply the questionnaires, and participants used their smartphones to fill them out during the session. The pre-test comprised parts A, B and C. Part A contained sociodemographic questions, Part B was access, digital skills, media literacy and digital knowledge, and Part C was uses and outcomes. The post-test comprised parts A, B and D – that is, sociodemographic questions (A), digital skills and digital knowledge (B), and future uses and outcomes (D). Excluding one atypical case, participants took on average almost 30 minutes to complete the pre-test, while the post-test took them almost 17 minutes. The outline of the data collection is presented below (see Figure 13).

Figure 13. Questionnaire application outline – CYF

For the first cohort in March, the application of the questionnaires was led by CYF volunteers. For the second round in April, one of the REMEDIS researchers was present for the pre- and post-tests to address any concerns related to the questionnaire, and to observe first-hand the potential difficulties that participants experienced with the instrument.

Sample

The pre-test was completed by 31 people whereas 18 people completed the post-test. All participants were encouraged to complete the questionnaire, but it was made clear that these activities would not affect the outcome of the course, so it was completed voluntarily.

Age: Respondents were on average 45 years old, with a range between 20 and 80.

Gender: 18 participants were female, 12 were male, and 1 person identified as 'Other'.

Education: Just over half the participants did not have a university degree; the rest declared having a graduate or postgraduate degree.

Occupation: A third were part-time students, and another third unemployed, 4 were part-time workers and 3 were retired, 2 were in full-time study, 2 were taking care of the home and children, and 1 was permanently sick or disabled. None of the participants reported to be working full-time at the time of the course. These results suggest that a large proportion of attendees may have experienced difficult financial circumstances due to not being in full-time work.

Language: The questionnaire did not ask about nationality or country of origin, but the researcher who attended the second session found that no participants were British nationals; rather they were from Iran, Syria, Afghanistan and Eritrea. As a result, English was not their first language, and in some cases, they required assistance from volunteers to translate and fill out the questionnaire.

The pre- and post-test samples were not made up of the exact same individuals, so conclusions about the effects of the intervention are partially subject to revision of the characteristics of both groups. For example, none of the participants declared that they were working in the post-test, while there were employed individuals in the pre-test.

3.12.2 Findings

Access

Almost all participants had a smartphone, which was key for the course as it was designed to teach participants how to use the device for everyday activities. However, smartphones might not be appropriate for certain activities, such as education or work-related tasks. This could negatively affect the expected outcomes of the intervention, given that participants would be less interested in using the internet for activities in these dimensions due to limited access to another device such as a laptop. Seventeen participants reported that the only device they had to access the internet was their smartphone.

Digital Literacy

The intervention presented a meaningful improvement in the participants' digital skills levels. The highest contribution was in technical and operational skills. Trainees indicated feeling more comfortable with the operation of their devices after the intervention, which is related to the fact that the course was designed to teach them how to use their smartphones in day-to-day activities. Information and communication skills both presented an increase of 18–19% of skills at a high level between pre- and post-test, while participants perceived fewer gains in content creation skills. During the three sessions, participants were taught how to find information online, how to be safe online and how to better use day-to-day apps, such as email and navigation, but no activities explored creating content. Participants indicated on feedback forms that they were interested in learning how to create content on social media.

Uses

An important increase was observed between current and intended future use (from 58% to 87% of activities enquired about), especially in the intention to use the internet for financial activities in the future. Given that the course includes teaching participants how to shop online and provides some advice on online banking, this increase in their confidence and overcoming some fears about the potential financial risks was not unexpected. During observations of the intervention, some participants expressed concerns about the closure of bank branches and the increasing need to shop online to get their desired products.

There was a notable difference in the use of the internet for work. Bearing in mind that some participants were older adults, and others had asylum seeker status, they might not be

interested in or allowed to get onto the job market. Participants reported not being interested in engaging for 11% of the wellbeing activities.

Relatively lower proportions of people not wanting to undertake these activities are due to a lack of adequate skills. Participants reported that they would not be able to do 7% of the wellbeing activities because they did not know how to do them.

Outcomes

The improvement in outcomes the participants expected to achieve was more modest than those observed in digital skills and future use, which suggests that increases in the level of digital skills and actual use for certain purposes does, in their eyes, not necessarily lead to positive outcomes, and that there are other obstacles in place. For instance, most participants were immigrants systematically experiencing obstacles to life in the UK, which digital skills and access to online services would not help them to be able to overcome.

One area in which they saw improvement was the internet's benefits for education purposes, since they were encouraged to enrol in additional learning opportunities to develop other skills.

3.12.3 Overall insights from the core REMEDIS questionnaire

Digital Literacy

The proportions of participants reporting high scores on every item were analysed, with an overall average of 19% of skills at a high level. In terms of particular domains, more participants reported having higher levels of communication and interaction skills (27%) than technical and operational (17%), information navigation (17%) and content creation (17%) skills.

In the post-test, the overall score was 39%, representing an increase of 20 percentage points in comparison to the pre-test. The highest proportion of people with skills at a high level was again in communication and interaction skills (45%), followed by technical and operational (45%), information navigation (36%) and content creation (29%).

Uses

Overall, participants reported in the pre-test to have undertaken 58% of the activities. Participants had undertaken many of the education-related activities (78%), followed by information seeking (73%), wellbeing (64%) and social (64%) activities. Finance (48%) and work (44%)-related activities were less likely to have been undertaken.

The order of types of engagement undertaken increased between pre- and post-test. Finance-related activities increased the most, with all respondents indicating that they would be using the internet for financial activities in the future. This was followed by education (90%), social (88%), informal learning (86%) and wellbeing (75%) activities.

Outcomes

In the pre-test, participants were satisfied with the outcomes of 66% of activities enquired about. Education was the dimension with the highest levels of satisfaction (83%). Therefore, the few people who did use the internet for education (n =9) had satisfactory experiences.

The likelihood of achieving finance and wellbeing outcomes was not as high as for education, with 73% of experiences in these areas expected to be positive. Nevertheless, 12 out of 15 participants who used the internet for financial purposes were happy with at least one of the two results of financial activities undertaken. Informal learning was also largely expected to have positive outcomes (72%), as were activities related to socialising (61%). However, participants were less likely to indicate that work-related activities (40%) undertaken online would lead to satisfactory outcomes. Only 7 out of 15 asserted that they were happy with at least one of two of the results of using the internet for work.

Participants did indicate that they would be likely to achieve satisfactory outcomes from their internet use after having participated in the intervention across all domains in the post-test. The highest score was education (87% of outcomes expected to be satisfactory), followed by information navigation (86%), wellbeing (79%), finance (79%) and social (73%) activities. The overall score was 77%.

3.12.4 Key insights

The findings revealed that even when improvements were observed in digital skills, uses and outcomes, those positive results were not equally distributed across all dimensions. Instead, the intervention had a positive effect, particularly in technical and informational digital skills and financial uses, for example. This is due to the format of the intervention, which focused on using participants' smartphones, and sessions aimed at using online shopping and mobile banking apps. Therefore, interventions should bear in mind that it might not be possible to achieve positive effects in all domains equally.

4 Concluding remarks

This report has provided an overview of the different evaluation activities carried out during the ML&DS interventions studied. Due to the wide variety of interventions and evaluations, while it is not possible to provide general conclusions and compare the impact of all the different interventions, a follow-up report (D3.2) looks at the evidence in each domain from a select group of interventions for which comparable data was available.

In this report, the improvements of each intervention and specific explanations based on the context of each intervention have been explored. These concluding remarks therefore remain very general, and the report is supposed to be read as a collection of short reports based on the specificities of each intervention. The partner organisations adopted different formats for the intervention as well as evaluation instruments. Some applied the full instruments in the pre- and post-tests, whereas others could only apply parts of the instrument in a post-test.

On the one hand, there were structural reasons organisations gave for not applying the full instruments. They were worried about asking questions not directly related to the content of the interventions since participants may be reluctant or unwilling to respond to these and become frustrated with the intervention itself. In contrast, others saw value in finding out whether their interventions had collateral effects in areas they were not expecting. This will help generate a broader sense of their impact, and make it possible to plan improvements

based on comprehensive evidence of tangible results rather than hypothesised results derived from having gained digital skills or increasing use.

However, the application of more comprehensive instruments also means increased organisational costs. It is often additional work for people (often volunteers) running the intervention, and can be exhausting for participants. Hence, organisations will have to find a fair balance between richer data, reasonable application times and human resources available.

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Appendix. Questionnaires

Part A. Sociodemographics and personal wellbeing

Intro [Such as: First, we would like to ask you some questions about yourself to understand the background of the people who are participating in our course/workshop/event]

1. In what year were you born? _____

2. How would you describe yourself? I am...

Male (0)	
Female (1)	
Non-binary (2)	
I would describe myself differently (please tell us how) (66)	
Prefer not to say (99) ⁶	

3. What is the **highest level of education** you have successfully completed? (If you finished your education abroad, please tick the option that is the most similar)⁷

Primary school level or lower (1)	
Secondary school level (O-Levels, CSE, GSCE, BTEC/SCOTVEC, RSA diploma, GNVQ, NVQ/SVQ up to Level 3, Apprenticeship, City and Guilds Craft, OND/ONC) (2)	
University entry level (AS-Level or equivalent, A-Level or equivalent, higher or equivalent, Scottish Sixth Year certificate, Access qualification) (3)	
Further education/vocational training (NVQ Levels 4 and 5, Foundation degree, Diploma in Higher Education, RSA higher diploma, HNC/HND, BTEC higher, Nursing qualification, other higher education below degree level) (4)	
Bachelor's degree (BA, BS, AB, etc.) (5)	
Graduate degree (Master's level, Doctorate) (6)	
Other (66)	
Prefer not to say (99)	

4. Which of the following best describes your current situation?

In full-time education (1)	
In part-time education (2)	
Working full-time (at least 30 hours a week) (3)	
Working part-time (8–29 hours a week) (4)	
Unemployed (5)	
Retired (6)	
Permanently sick or disabled (7)	
In community or military service (8)	

⁶ Answer category coding should not be shown to participants. All 'Other's are to be marked 66, 'Don't know's 77, 'Not applicable's 88 and 'Prefer not to say' 99.

⁷ Although this should be adopted for the particular country, at the very minimum it should classify the education level up to secondary school, undergraduate (BA), further (post-secondary) and graduate (MSc/PhD) education levels.

Taking care of the home, looking after children or other people (9)	
Other (66)	

5. Please indicate how true the following statements are of yourself.

	Not true of me (1)	Not very true of me (2)	Mostly true of me (3)	Very true of me (4)	Don't know (77)	Don't want to answer (99)
I am able to participate well at work (1) ⁸						
I am able to participate well in class (2) ⁹						
I feel I am behind on what is happening in the world (3)						
I am generally a confident person (4)						
I know how to manage my finances (e.g., banking, budgeting) (5) ¹⁰						
If I need help, there is someone I can call for support (6)						
I would like to be in contact with family and friends more (7)						
I am able to make informed decisions about my health (8)						
I have a tendency to feel lonely (9)						
I know where to go to get things done (e.g., get a driver's license, find out about tax benefits) (10)						

⁸ For those who have indicated that they are employed.

⁹ For those who have indicated that they are in education.

¹⁰ Only for adults (> 18 years old).

Part B. Digital lived environment

The questions in this section are related to the internet access conditions you have, what you know, and what you actually do online.

We would like to ask you a few questions about how you use the internet and technologies such as mobile phones and computers.

1. Which of these do you use to access the internet? (Select all that apply)

Computer (desktop or laptop) (1)	
Smartphone (a phone that you can access the internet with or download apps on) (2)	
Tablet or eReader (e.g., iPad, Kindle, etc.) (3)	
Game console (e.g., Xbox, PlayStation, etc.) (4)	
None of these (5)	
Other (please give a description) (66)	

2. Please indicate **how true the following statements are of you** when thinking about how you use the internet and technologies such as mobile phones.

If you have never done this, think about how true this would be of you **if you had to do it now, and by yourself.**

If you do not understand what the question is asking, tick the box 'I do not understand what you mean by this'.

	Not at all true of me (1)	Not very true of me (2)	Neither true nor untrue of me (3)	Mostly true of me (4)	Very true of me (5)	I do not understand what you mean by this (0)	I do not want to answer (99)
I know how to protect a device (e.g., with a PIN, a screen pattern, a fingerprint, facial recognition) (1)							
I know how to store photos, documents or other files on the cloud (e.g., Google Drive, iCloud) (2)							
I know how to use private browsing (e.g., incognito mode) (3)							

3. Please indicate how true the following statements are of you when thinking about how you use the internet and technologies such as mobile phones.

If you have never done this, think about how true this would be of you if you had to do it now, and by yourself.

	Not at all true of me (1)	Not very true of me (2)	Neither true nor untrue of me (3)	Mostly true of me (4)	Very true of me (5)	I do not understand what you mean by this (0)	I do not want to answer (99)
I know how to use advanced search functions in search engines (1)							
I know how to check if the information I find online is true (2)							
I know how to figure out if a website can be trusted (3)							

4. Please indicate **how true the following statements are of you** when thinking about how you use the internet and technologies such as mobile phones.
 If you have never done this, think about how true this would be of you **if you had to do it now, and by yourself**.
 If you do not understand what the question is asking, tick the box 'I do not understand what you mean by this'.

	Not at all true of me (1)	Not very true of me (2)	Neither true nor untrue of me (3)	Mostly true of me (4)	Very true of me (5)	I do not understand what you mean by this (0)	I do not want to answer (99)
Depending on the situation, I know which medium or tool to use to communicate with someone (e.g., make a call, send a WhatsApp message, send an email) (1)							
I know which images and information about me is okay to share online (2)							
I know when it is and when it is not appropriate to use emoticons (e.g., smileys, emojis), text speak (e.g., LOL, OMG) and capital letters (3)							

5. Please indicate **how true the following statements are of you** when thinking about how you use the internet and technologies such as mobile phones.
If you have never done this, then think about how true this would be of you **if you had to do it now, and by yourself.**

	Not at all true of me (1)	Not very true of me (2)	Neither true nor untrue of me (3)	Mostly true of me (4)	Very true of me (5)	I do not understand what you mean by this (0)	I do not want to answer (99)
I know how to create something that combines different digital media (e.g., photos, music, videos, GIFs) (1)							
I know how to edit existing digital images, music and videos (2)							
I know how to ensure that many people will see what I put online (3)							

6. To what extent are the following statements about media such as television, radio, newspapers and how people use them true or not true?
If you are not sure, please let us know.

	Definitely not true (1)	Definitely true (2)	I am not sure (3)	I do not want to answer (99)
Media companies choose content based on what will attract the biggest audience (1)				
Documentaries are made to represent what really happened in an unbiased way (2)				
People are more likely to be persuaded by media content that fits with their own views than by media content that doesn't (3)				
Media content and platforms are designed in such a way to keep people hooked/paying attention (4)				
A story about peace is more likely to be featured prominently than one about war (5)				

7. To what extent are the following statements about technologies such as the internet and mobile phones true or not true? If you are not sure, please let us know.

	Definitely not true (1)	Definitely true (2)	I am not sure (3)	I do not want to answer (99)
The first search result presented by search engines (such as Google or Bing) is always the best information source (1)				
Everyone gets the same information when they search for things online (2)				
Whether someone likes or shares a post can have a negative impact on others (3)				
The first post a person sees on social media is the last thing that was posted by one of their contacts (4)				
Using hashtags (#) increases the visibility of a post (5)				
Companies pay ordinary people to use their products in videos and content they create (6)				

Part C. Uses and outcomes

Intro: The following questions are about the things you do or do not do with technologies such as the internet and mobile phones, and what the outcomes are of this use.

Informal learning

1. Thinking about your online activities (on the internet or mobile phone) **in the last month**, please indicate whether the following was something you did – something that happened and whether you were happy with the result (i.e., whether you learned something).

	No, I haven't tried to do this (1)	Yes, I did this but was not happy with most results (2)	Yes, I did this and was overall happy with what I found (3)	I don't want to answer (99)
I looked up information online to answer a question I had (1)				
I came across opinions that differed from my own (e.g., in newspapers, on discussion boards, social media) (2)				

Wellbeing

2. We would like to know whether you have tried to do any of the following activities **in the last month**, and whether you were happy with the result (i.e., whether you improved your life or knowledge).

	No, I haven't tried to do this (1)	Yes, I did this but was not happy with most results (2)	Yes, I did this and was overall happy with the results (3)	I don't want to answer (99)
Look up information to understand problems or issues that interest you (1)				
Use sport or fitness-related advice or programs/apps (2)				
Look up health-related information/advice online (3)				

3. Have you come across any of the following things on the internet or your mobile phone **in the last month**?

	Yes (1)	No (2)	I don't want to answer this question (99)
I have come across content that offended me (1)			
On the internet, I found information that made me do things that were not so good for my health (2)			

Social

4. We would like to know whether you did any of the following activities or whether they happened to you online **in the last month**, and if you were happy with how it went or felt (in comparison with your offline interactions).

	No, I haven't tried to do this (1)	Yes, I did this but was not happy with most interactions (2)	Yes, I did this and was happy with most interactions (3)	I don't want to answer (99)
Communicated with my close family and friends (1)				
Contacted people who are not close friends or family (2)				
Looked for information on a government or public service (e.g., taxes, benefits, driving licence) (3)				

5. Have any of the following happened to you on the internet or through a mobile phone **in the last month**?

	Yes (1)	No (2)	I don't want to answer this question (99)
Other people on the internet have sent me annoying or embarrassing messages (1)			
The internet and mobile phone have made interacting with others more difficult for me (2)			

Finance (only for adults 18+)

6. We would like to know whether you have tried to do any of the following activities **in the last month**, and whether you were happy with the result (i.e., you managed to get the service or product you wanted).

	No, I haven't tried to do this (1)	Yes, I did this but was not happy with most results (2)	Yes, I did this and was happy with most services or products (3)	I don't want to answer (99)
Buy products or services online (1)				
Use financial services (e.g., benefits advice, banking, finding insurance) online (2)				

7. Have any of the following things happened to you on the internet or on your mobile phone **in the last month**?

	Yes (1)	No (2)	I don't want to answer this question (99)
I have bought products online that were of bad quality (1)			
I have lost money on the internet due to fraud or a scam (2)			

Occupation – Education (for students only)¹¹

8. We would like to know whether you have tried to do any of the following things in relation to school/university **in the last month**, and if you were happy with how it went or felt (i.e., you managed to find what you were looking for/used the tools in a satisfactory way).

	No, I haven't tried to do this (1)	Yes, I did this but was not happy with most results (2)	Yes, I did this and was happy with most results (3)	I don't want to answer (99)
Searched for information online to do homework (1)				
Used online tools for school/university work (e.g., Moodle, Blackboard) (2)				

9. Has the following happened to you in relation to school/university work **in the last month**?

	Yes (1)	No (2)	I don't want to answer this question (99)
I had trouble getting school materials or documents I needed for school/university that were available online or sent by email (1)			
The technology I have is of too poor quality to be able to do homework or assignments (2)			

¹¹ The following questions are either/or – that is, in the Occupation questions, people get only one question set – either the Education, Work or Unemployed question, unless you have space for more.

Occupation – Work (everybody else can be asked this, not just people working)

10. We would like to know whether you have had paid employment or done voluntary work of any kind **in the last month**.¹²

Yes, I have done paid, unpaid or volunteer work (1)	
No, I have not done any paid, unpaid or volunteer work (2)	

11. Please indicate whether you have tried to do the following things for your work **in the last month**, and what the result was of this use of technologies, such as the internet and mobile phone.

	No, I haven't tried to do this (1)	Yes, I did this but was not very happy with how this allowed me to do the work (2)	Yes, I did this and was mostly happy with how this allowed me to do the work (3)	I don't want to answer (99)
Used the internet or mobile phone for my work (1)				
Searched for information online related to my work (2)				

12. Has any of the following happened to you in relation to your work **in the last month**?

	Yes (1)	No (2)	I don't want to answer this question (99)
I had trouble getting information or documents for work that were available online or sent by email (1)			
The internet and/or mobile phone force me to work in a certain way that I do not like (2)			

¹² This should only be asked if those who are retired, disabled or doing care work at home are given the Work questions.

Occupation – Unemployed (for those who are unemployed; if there is space, also ask those who are employed)

13. Please indicate whether you have tried to do the following things **in the last month**, what the result was of this use of technologies, such as the internet and mobile phone, and how satisfied you were with the result.

	No, I haven't tried to do this (1)	Yes, I did this but was not happy with most results (2)	Yes, I did this and was mostly happy with the result (3)	I don't want to answer (99)
I looked for a job online (1)				
I created a profile on a job site (e.g., LinkedIn, Indeed) (2)				

14. Has any of the following happened to you **in the past month**?

	Yes (1)	No (2)	I don't want to answer this question (99)
I saw jobs I liked but did not apply for them because they require technical skills or certifications that I don't have (1)			
I haven't got a response to a position I applied for online in the previous six months (2)			
I have been rejected for a job that I applied for online (3)			

Thank you for answering these questions. There are no more questions we have for you.

Please let us know if there is anything you would like to add.

Part D. Uses and outcomes (post-intervention immediate)

Informal learning

1. Thinking about the following online activities (on the internet or mobile phone), please indicate how likely you are to do this **in the coming months**:

	No, I will not because I am not interested (1)	No, I will not because I don't know how (2)	Yes, I might do this (3)	Yes, I will definitely do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)	This doesn't apply to me (88)
Look up information online to answer a question I have (1)						
Look for information which has opinions that are different from my own (e.g., in newspapers, on discussion boards, social media) (2)						

2. After taking this course, do you know how to achieve the following?

	No (1)	I am not sure (2)	Yes, I already managed to do this (3)	Yes, I will now manage to do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)
Find quality information about something I am interested in online (1)					
Avoid being misled by fake news or misleading information online (2)					

Wellbeing

Here are a number of activities someone might do online. Were you able to do these before the course? And now, would you be able to do these?

3. Thinking about the following online activities (on the Internet or mobile phones), please indicate how likely you are to do this **in the coming months**.

	No, I will not because I am not interested (1)	No, I will not because I still don't know how (2)	Yes, I might do this (3)	Yes, I will definitely do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)	This doesn't apply to me (88)
I will use the internet and apps to get health advice (1)						
I will use the internet and apps for fitness (2)						

4. Can you manage to do the following?

	No (1)	I am not sure (2)	Yes, I already managed to do this before the course (3)	Yes, I now know how to do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)
Avoid apps or websites that expose me to harmful content (1)					
Find information that helps me make decisions that are good for my health (2)					

Social

Here are a number of activities someone might do online. Were you able to do these before the course? And now, would you be able to do these?

5. Thinking about the following online activities (on the Internet or mobile phones), please indicate how likely you are to do this in the coming months.

	No, I will not because I am not interested (1)	No, I will not because I still don't know how (2)	Yes, I might do this (3)	Yes, I will definitely do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)	This doesn't apply to me (88)
I will communicate with my family and friends online (1)						
I will use internet to get in touch with other people to solve a problem I face (e.g. council, utilities provider, medical practice) (2)						

6. Can you manage to do the following?

	No (1)	I am not sure (2)	Yes, I already managed to do this before the course (3)	Yes, I now know how to do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)
Take positive action if I or someone I know is being bullied/harassed online (1)					
Engaging in productive discussions around social issues with others on the internet or mobile apps (2)					

Occupation – Work

Here are a number of activities someone might do online. Were you able to do these before the course? And now, would you be able to do these?

7. Thinking about the following online activities (on the Internet or mobile phones), please indicate how likely you are to do this in the coming months.

	No, I will not because I am not interested (1)	No, I will not because I still don't know how (2)	Yes, I might do this (3)	Yes, I will definitely do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)	This doesn't apply to me (88)
I will use Internet and my phone for work-related issues (1)						
I will create a profile on a job site (e.g. LinkedIn, Indeed) (2)						

8. Can you do the following?

	No (1)	I am not sure (2)	Yes, I already knew how to do this (3)	Yes, I now know how to do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)
Managing my use of the internet so that I am more productive in my job (1)					
Networking with other people in ways that benefit work-related activities (e.g. LinkedIn, Zoom) (2)					

Occupation – Education

Here are a number of activities someone might do online. Were you able to do these before the course? And now, would you be able to do these?

9. Thinking about the following online activities (on the Internet or mobile phones), please indicate how likely you are to do this in the coming months.

	No, I will not because I am not interested (1)	No, I will not because I still don't know how (2)	Yes, I might do this (3)	Yes, I will definitely do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)	This doesn't apply to me (88)
I will use internet to find study materials that I wouldn't find at the school/library (1)						
I will sign up for other courses online (2)						

10. Can you manage to do the following?

	No (1)	I am not sure (2)	Yes, I already managed to do this before the course (3)	Yes, I now know how to do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)
Use the internet in ways that improve my performance on the course or at school (i.e. better presentations, better grades, hand in assignments)					
Avoid getting lost on the different platforms used to collaborate with fellow students and teachers (2a) [for those in formal education]					
Avoid missing out on digital learning opportunities (2b) [for those taking online courses]					

Finance

Here are a number of activities someone might do online. Were you able to do these before the course? And now, would you be able to do these?

11. Thinking about the following online activities (on the Internet or mobile phones), please indicate how likely you are to do this in the coming months.

	No, I will not because I am not interested (1)	No, I will not because I still don't know how (2)	Yes, I might do this (3)	Yes, I will definitely do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)	This doesn't apply to me (88)
I will use internet to buy a product or service online (1)						
I will compare products and services on different websites (2)						

12. After taking this course, do you know how to do the following?

	No (1)	I am not sure (2)	Yes, I already knew how to do this (3)	Yes, I now know how to do this (4)	I don't want to answer (99)
Save money by finding better prices for products and services online (1)					
Avoid being a victim of a scam or fraud (2)					

